

NEWSROOM TO GOVERNMENT: THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF FORMER MEDIA PRACTITIONERS TO PUBLIC SERVICE DELIVERY TOWARDS THE ENHANCEMENT OF TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY IN THE BUREAUCRACY

Charissa Luci-Atienza

Graduate School of Business, University of Perpetual Help System DALTA, Las Piñas City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The study zeroed in on former media practitioners' significant roles and contributions to public service delivery towards the enhancement of transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy. It explored how the migration of former print, broadcast, and multimedia journalists to the government contributed to the delivery of transparent and accountable delivery of public services. The study employed Qualitative Research Design, specifically transcendental phenomenology, to look into and document newsroom-to-government experiences of the 15 research participants in 10 government agencies and institutions. The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique to choose the participants, and used a self-designed and detailed questionnaire, and one-on-one, semi-structured key informant interview sessions as research instruments. The qualitative data collected were manually analyzed, using a combination of narrative and thematic analysis. Based on the study's findings, the participants are mostly print journalists, and are Millennials and Generation X, and majority of whom left their media profession mainly due to economic reasons. Most participants are heavily involved in the delivery of public information services as public communicators for the policies, projects, and programs being implemented by Executive agencies, and Congress. An enhancement policy seeking to strengthen the Public Information Offices (PIOs) of every government agency and instrumentalities by accelerating the level of communications in the public sector through continued skills upgrading; and the creation of fora where they can share best practices, was proposed to strengthen the involvement of former media practitioners in the transparent and accountable delivery of public service.

Keywords: *Former Media Practitioners, Contributions, Public Service Delivery, Transparency, Accountability, Bureaucracy*

INTRODUCTION

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic not only changed the country's political, and socio-economic scene, but also significantly affected the national media landscape. During this period, several key events affecting national and even local media or press happened, including closure of broadcast networks, newsroom layoffs, and overhauls of radio and television (TV) programming, particularly during the government's imposition of lockdowns and quarantines. Economic losses forced the print media sector to suspend their print editions and prioritize strengthening their online presence. Most of the news outlets implemented work-from-home policies, with some adopting skeletal staffing arrangements.

The COVID-19 caught the news media sector flat-footed, given the declining revenues, and the need to tap digital technology to reach out to ballooning social media users. The traditional economic model of journalism which considered advertising revenues and subscriptions as its lifeblood was disrupted by the emergence of digital platforms such as Google and Meta (formerly Facebook), which now control more than half of the global digital advertising market (Westberg, 2024).

Aside from newsroom downsizing, journalists and media workers had faced harassments, imprisonments, and attacks for their doing their job as watchdogs (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2022). Examples include the arrest of Nobel Peace Prize laureate Maria Ressa over tax evasion charges and cyber libel charges, and the infamous killing of famous broadcaster and radio commentator Percy Lapid, highlighting state-sanctioned attacks against journalists.

Amid this challenging media landscape during COVID-19, a number of media practitioners left their profession to join the government service. It was during the pandemic that the transfer of media practitioners to government was remarkably observed.

The Philippine government as the most secured employer during the pandemic welcomed into its arms members of "fourth estate" or the media to be part of its working force. But even before the pandemic, it has been noted that there were broadcast media personalities who entered government through election such as Vice President Noli de Castro and Senator Loren Legarda.

This study aimed at exploring the migration of private media practitioners (the traditional print media, broadcast media covering both radio and TV, and multimedia) to the government service. While there were articles on the cases of media personalities entering the government service and even politics, the reasons behind this trend and its impact on the delivery of government services remained largely unexplored.

There is no available, and official data yet on the total number of journalists from the private sector who entered the government service. The National Union of Journalists of the Philippines, National Press Club (NPC), the Presidential Task Force on Media Security (PTFoMS), and the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) relayed to this UPHSD researcher that they do not have the data on the total number of Filipino journalists who lost their jobs or resigned during the pandemic, and who entered the government service. Moreover, the total number of Filipino journalists in the Philippines is also not yet available, according to the NUJP Secretariat, NPC president Leonel Abasola, and PTFoMS Executive Director Paul M. Gutierrez.

As to the number of media outlets under the mainstream or traditional media, Gutierrez disclosed that more than half or 53 percent are radio stations (735), followed by 421 newspapers at 30 percent; 162 television and cable stations at 12 percent; and 73 magazines at five percent, citing the Philippine Information Agency (PIA) data as of July 2023 (Rita, 2024). Rita (2024) reported “the thousands” of media outlets utilizing social media platforms were not included in the total number of media outlets.

The roles and contributions of former journalists in their respective government agencies cannot be overstressed. The study sought to determine as to whether the inclusion of the “fourth estate” or the media in the 1.7 million-strong state workforce is beneficial for the government, particularly in the transparent and accountable delivery of public service.

As of 30 June 2023, the Inventory of the Government Human Resource System (IGHRS) recorded 1, 973, 300 workers (Civil Service Commission’s Integrated Records Management Office, 2023). Of the total, 1,751,975 workers have secured career positions, and 221, 325 have occupied non-career positions (Civil Service Commission’s Inventory of Government Human Resource – Career and Non-Career, 2023, p.1). A total of 832,812 personnel were hired under Job-order (JO) and Contract of Service (COS) status (Civil Service Commission’s Inventory of Government Human Resource – JO/COS Data, 2023).

Considering the need for more empirical evidence on the former media practitioners’ perceptions about public service delivery, this study aimed at probing these gaps by digging into their roles and contributions to public service delivery, particularly in the fulfillment of their respective agencies’ mandate. Data on this aspect is warranted, as this could boost the potential of government’s workforce particularly in the aspect of effectively and efficiently disseminating the programs and projects of the national government, as well as in the national government’s fight against corruption, and campaign for transparency and accountability.

To come up with comprehensive interpretation and analysis of the impending issues on the migration of private media practitioners to government service, parameters were set for the clear appreciation of the respondents’ profile as to their age, gender, length of media experience; media affiliation or news outfit (Print, Broadcast, or Multimedia); Government Agency-Employer (Executive, Legislative, Judiciary or

Independent Public Institution); and Position (Executive, Managerial, Supervisory, or Non-Supervisory).

This paper explored ways on how former media practitioners can effectively engage with the government to curb corruption, and promoting transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy. Likewise, this study developed an enhancement policy that could strengthen the involvement of former media practitioners in the transparent and accountable delivery of public service.

Research Questions

This study aimed to scrutinize the country's media landscape, analyzing the political, social, economic, and personal factors that prompted the media practitioners to leave their job and enter the government service.

This study delved into the roles and contributions of former media practitioners to public service delivery, and to the dissemination and promotion of government's programs and projects in general, and their perception about the delivery of public service.

This paper necessitated the former media practitioners to effectively engage with the government as partners in disseminating its programs and projects to curb corruption, and promote transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy. This study aimed at developing an enhancement policy that could strengthen the involvement of former media practitioners in promoting transparency and accountability in public service delivery.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

For purposes of determining the appropriate coding strategy, the following demographics were determined.

- Age;
- Gender;
- Length of Service as Media Practitioner;
- Media Outfits (Print, Broadcast, or Multimedia);
- Government Agency-Employer (Executive, Legislative, Judiciary or Independent Public Institution); and
- Position (Executive, Managerial, Supervisory, or Non-Supervisory).

1. What are the reasons behind the migration of print, broadcast and multimedia journalists to the government service in terms of:

- 1.1. political
- 1.2. economic
- 1.3. social
- 1.4. personal?

2. What are the roles of former media practitioners in their respective agencies?

3. What are the perceptions of former media practitioners about public service delivery?
 4. What are the former journalists' contributions to public service delivery, particularly in the fulfillment of their agencies' mandate?
 5. How can former journalists effectively engage with the government as partners in disseminating its programs and projects to curb corruption, and promote transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy?
 6. What policy can be developed to enhance and strengthen the involvement of former media practitioners in promoting transparency and accountability in public service delivery?
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METHODOLOGY

This study focused on the major issues and concerns behind the transfer of former media practitioners to government agencies, and their contributions and roles to public service delivery towards the enhancement of transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy.

Scope, Research Locale, and Delimitations/Limitations of the Study

The locale of the study was confined to Metro Manila where major media companies and key government offices and institutions are located.

The study was conducted in nine (9) government agencies and institutions under the Executive, Legislative, and Judicial branches of government, and in one (1) independent public financial institution where fifteen (15) former media practitioners from print, broadcast, and multimedia news sectors are currently working.

Not all former journalists formed part of the study, considering the lack of official data on the total number of Filipino journalists in the country, and the total number of media practitioners who left their profession and entered the government service.

Although, the study took note of the participants' previous media affiliations and years of experience in the news media sector covering the three branches of government: Executive, Legislative, and the Judiciary.

The study only covered the concerned individuals and not their respective agencies. Other issues and concerns related to migration of former journalists to the public sector, and to the private sector were not be thoroughly studied due to time restraint and constrained resources of the researcher.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were fifteen (15) former media practitioners, especially those field reporters, who left their profession, and are currently working in nine (9) government agencies and institutions under the Executive, Legislative, and Judicial branches of government, and in one (1) independent public financial institution.

This study looked into their contributions and roles to public service delivery towards the enhancement of transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy via an in-depth one-on-one interview.

Fifteen (15) former media practitioners who worked for Metro Manila-based media organizations were interviewed based on the following inclusion criteria:

- 1) Worked as a field news reporter or news writer affiliated with print, broadcast (either radio or television), and multimedia companies in Metro Manila;
- 2) Covered any of the following branches of government: Executive, Legislative, and Judiciary as beat assignment;
- 3) Had experience in any of the following areas: broadcast, online, documentaries or investigative, public service program or political reporting; and
- 4) Working in the government regardless of the status of appointment.

The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique to choose the participants of this study and determine their credentials to ensure that they were credible and key sources of factual information, and were qualified to share their inputs and opinions about the research topic.

Demographic Profile of Participants

Amid the use of qualitative approach, the researcher found it significant to know the demographic profile of the participants to fully describe the phenomenon in the study.

These include age, gender, length of service as a media practitioner, previous media outfit or affiliation (Print, Broadcast, or Multimedia), Government Agency-Employer (Executive, Legislative, Judiciary or Independent Public Institution), and Position (Executive, Managerial, Supervisory, or Non-Supervisory).

As to the length of service as a media practitioner, the researcher, as advised by the Research Panel, decided to put a bracket to track down participants' career record in the private sector.

Based on the years of media service in the private sector, the participants were clustered as follows: a. 5 years and below; b. 6-10 years; and c. 11-20 years or more.

These variables were vital for the determination of appropriate coding strategy, creation of the anchor code for each research question, and identification of the relevant excerpts. In this way, there was clear labeling of the codes.

Research Instrument

A critical informant interview guide for the respondents was prepared. The researcher used Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) as a data collection method.

The self-designed and detailed questionnaire zeroed in on the political, social, economic, and personal issues and concerns that prompted the 'fourth estate' members to leave their media profession and enter the government service.

It also focused on the roles and contributions of former journalists in their respective government agencies. It likewise delved into the importance of having media persons in the 1.7 million-strong state workforce, particularly in the delivery of public service.

The researcher used the questionnaire and interview sessions as the research instruments.

Conducting one-on-one interview is needed to excavate crucial and in-depth information from the research participants.

A semi-structured interview was used as a "more powerful" tool to obtain detailed information and evidence from the respondents while considering the focus of the study (Ruslin et al., 2022). The conduct of semi-structured interview due to its flexibility allowed the researcher to bring forward new questions during the interview as a consequence of what the research participants have said.

Reliability and Validation of the Instrument

As the main instrument in the study, the self-designed and detailed questionnaire underwent a stringent validation process. First and foremost, the researcher submitted the questionnaire to the research adviser for review, and comments and suggestions were elicited for fine-tuning.

The interview guide questions were validated by experts on the field of public administration and communications.

The valuable insights of the content validators were pertinent to researcher's quest to have reliable and valid research instrument.

The inputs made by the adviser, Research Panel, and the content validators, particularly the comments and suggestions, were thoroughly considered and included in the questionnaire for its relevance and validity.

Data Generation

After formally securing the green light from the Research Panel and the University of Perpetual Help System- DALTA (UPHSD) Graduate School on 14 July 2024, the researcher proceeded to data gathering, mindful that the reasons why former media practitioners flocked to government service and the determination of their contributions to the delivery of public service were to be described under phenomenological approach.

The researcher prepared a critical informant interview guide for the research participants that included a set of clear, concise, and relevant questions in sync with the research objectives.

The questions prodded the respondents to share their transition from the newsroom grind to government service delivery; the reasons behind their migration to government; their perception about public service delivery; their contributions to public service delivery; and their suggestions regarding the strengthening of their partnership with the government in curbing corruption, and in promoting transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy, and on how to fortify their involvement in promoting transparency and accountability in public service delivery.

After the validation of the questionnaire by the research adviser, Research panel, and experts on the field of public administration and communications, the letter request to conduct the study, and the questionnaire coupled with informed consent form and certificate indicating that the respondents' participation in the study is entirely voluntary, were sent out to the respondents via e-mail and FB messenger from July 21 to July 26, 2024.

Twelve (12) respondents received these documents through e-mail, while three (3) participants got them through FB messenger as their preferred mode of transmittal.

The researcher individually contacted the randomly selected respondents for their preferred interview schedule via e-mail, Facebook messenger, and Viber.

Anticipating the busy schedule of the probable respondents, the researcher made an initial *tête-à-tête* or private conversation with some of them so as to gauge their willingness to participate in the study during the last week of June.

Some of them even referred their colleagues in the government service who could participate in the study.

The researcher formally sought a written or verbal permission from the participants before conducting the face-to-face interviews.

Three (3) respondents managed to sign the Consent Certificate, while the rest opted to signify their voluntary participation by responding affirmatively to the e-mailed letter request, and by saying "Yes" before the start of the Zoom-recorded interview.

The purpose of the study was explained to the respondents in various communication channels. Before conducting the interview, the researcher made sure that the respondents positively responded and voluntarily gave their consent to be part of the study.

The researcher likewise assured the participants that confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity were strictly observed, and that Zoom recordings both audio and video, and all data and information collected were solely used for the research analysis, and scholarly pursuits.

The researcher conducted the in-depth interviews via Zoom from July 23 to July 27, 2024. The interviews lasted 15 to 75 minutes, and were recorded for documentation, transcription, analysis, and decoding.

During the interviews, the researcher took notes to capture unpredictable themes, uncover more insights, and bring forward additional new questions as a follow-up to the information, data, or narratives previously provided by the respondents.

After the interviews, the researcher transcribed verbatim the narratives, and carefully took a second look at notes to ensure accuracy, and to gain a comprehensive understanding of the issues at hand.

Thematic Reflections

Using a combination of narrative and thematic analysis, the qualitative data collected were manually analyzed to find common themes and patterns of occurrence in the responses made by the respondents.

The experiences that were divulged by the research participants were interpreted based on the context of this research. Using the descriptive-focused coding strategy, the researcher engaged in coding the data; identifying, reviewing, refining, defining, and naming the themes.

All relevant excerpts were highlighted and were given a designated code. The researcher likewise managed to establish the link of a new code to existing code.

As part of qualitative data analysis technique such as content analysis, the participants' answers to each question were coded and categorized.

After categorizing the codes, the researcher consolidated the categories and arranged them alphabetically in matrix format via MS Word. A code count was then assigned to identify frequency counts or how many times such particular code was repetitively mentioned by the participants.

Code sorting involved the clustering of answers in a tabular format, while cluster labelling was done to determine the themes for discussion (Adu, 2021).

The researcher found it necessary to allot at least more time for the coding and processing of themes in the coding-recoding process until the final theme was arrived at.

After thoroughly reflecting on the themes in the narratives, the researcher was bound to present the significant insights or findings into the lived experiences of the participants while mindful of the research purpose and the research questions that must be addressed. From these essential insights and findings, conclusions and recommendations were objectively drawn.

RESULTS

The information and the data that were collected, including the narratives of the respondents were presented in text and tabular format.

The systematic presentation of the data was in sync and corresponded to the research questions under the Statement of the Problem, paving the way for evidence-based findings, informed conclusions and data-driven recommendations.

The study, "Newsroom to Government: The Contributions of Former Media Practitioners to Public Service Delivery Towards the Enhancement of Transparency and Accountability in the Bureaucracy," aimed at providing an in-depth analysis of the political, social, economic, and personal issues and concerns that prompted the media practitioners to leave their job and enter the government service.

Furthermore, the study also delved into their roles and contributions to public service delivery, as part of the suggested recommendation to enhance transparency and accountability of the bureaucracy.

Fifteen (15) former journalists working in Metro Manila took part as participants (P) in this study as key informants (as shown in Table 1).

In terms of age, the participants are within the ages of 25 and 58 — three of them belong to the 25 - 35 age brackets; six belong to 36 - 46 age brackets; six belong to 47 - 57 age brackets.

Of the total, seven participants are male, and eight are women.

Based on their profiles, seven participants had extensive media experience ranging from 10 years to 20 years.

Based on the years of media service in the private sector, the participants were categorized as follows: A. 5 years and below; B. 6-10 years; and C. 11-20 years or more.

Following this category, seven participants fall under Category B, five under Category C, and three under Category A.

Data shows that most participants belong to Category B (6 – 10 years) with a media experience ranging from six to 10 years.

During the data gathering, it was uncovered that three participants left their media profession to join the government service during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In terms of media affiliations, nine participants worked as print media journalists, three were employed at multimedia news platforms, and remaining three participants were broadcast journalists.

In terms of government-employer, eight participants are working at agencies under the Executive branch of government, while five are with the Legislative. The two remaining participants work in the Judiciary, and in an independent government financial institution, respectively.

In terms of government positions, most participants are holding key, supervisory, and permanent positions in their respective agencies.

Given the flexibility of the semi-structured interview employed by the researcher, the stints of the participants in their current government agency were uncovered. Eight participants have been working in the government for 10 to 25 years.

The participants' names, media organizations, government agency-employers and current specific positions were not revealed and were kept confidential. The 15 respondents were given aliases (P1 to P15).

All Zoom-recorded interviews which lasted 15 to 75 minutes were held from July 23 to July 27, 2024 with the informed consent of the participants.

Participant 1 worked as print media journalist for 15 years, and has been working in an agency under the Executive branch of government for 25 years.

Participant 2 was affiliated with a broadcast media company, had a nine-year stint in the news media sector, and has been serving an Executive agency for 16 years.

Participant 3 worked at the broadcast news media with 20 years of media experience, held the post of Undersecretary, and is working in the Legislative branch of government.

Participant 4 is a former print journalist for 10 years, and has been working in the Legislative for 14 years.

Participant 5 was with the print media for seven (7) years, and has been working in the Judiciary for 22 years.

Participant 6 was a print journalist for five (5) years before serving the government for 14 years, and has been with an Executive agency.

Participant 7 had a print media experience of six (6) years, and has been working in an independent government financial institution for 16 years.

Participant 8 came from print news media sector with eight (8) years of experience, and has been working in an Executive agency.

Participant 9 was print journalist for 13 years and has been with an Executive agency for six (6) years.

Participant 10 worked with a broadcast media company, had a media experience of 11 years, and has been working in the government for 20 years.

Participant 11 was affiliated with a broadcast media company for 20 years, and has been with an Executive agency for three (3) years.

Participant 12 had a one-year stint in a newspaper company, and has been working with an Executive agency for four (4) years.

Participant 13 worked at a multimedia news platform for six (6) years, and has been with the Legislative for three (3) years.

Participant 14 was a multimedia journalist for 10 years, and has been working in the Legislative for three (3) years.

Participant 15 was a print journalist for four (4) years, and has been affiliated with an Executive agency for three (3) years.

Table 1

Profile of the Former Media Practitioners in Metro Manila

Alias	Age	Gender	Years in Media	Media Outfit	Gov't Agency	Position	Years in Gov't
P1	57	M	15	Print	Executive	Executive	25
P2	47	F	9	Broadcast	Executive	Executive	16
P3	47	M	20	Broadcast	Legislative	Managerial	1
P4	49	M	10	Print	Legislative	Supervisory	14
P5	50	M	7	Print	Judiciary	Supervisory	22
P6	43	F	5	Print	Executive	Supervisory	14
P7	43	F	6	Print	Independent Financial Institution	Managerial	16
P8	43	M	8	Print	Executive	Supervisory	17
P9	45	F	13	Print	Executive	Supervisory	6
P10	53	M	11	Multimedia	Legislative	Managerial	20
P11	39	F	20	Broadcast	Executive	Supervisory	3
P12	25	F	1	Print	Executive	Non-Supervisory	4
P13	29	F	6	Multimedia	Legislative	Non-Supervisory	3
P14	37	M	10	Multimedia	Legislative	Non-Supervisory	3
P15	27	F	4	Print	Executive	Non-Supervisory	3

This study is grouped into six major segments to correspond to the research questions under the Statement of the Problem (SOP): (1) Political, economic, social, and personal reasons behind the migration of print, broadcast and multimedia journalists to the government service; (2) Roles of former media practitioners in their respective agencies; (3) Perceptions about public service delivery; (4) Contributions to public service delivery; (5) Suggestions to strengthen partnership to curb corruption, and promote transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy, and (6) Policies to be recommended for promotion of transparent and accountable public service delivery.

I. Reasons Behind the Migration of Print, Broadcast and Multimedia Journalists to the Government Service

What are the reasons behind the migration of print, broadcast and multimedia journalists to the government service in terms of:

1.1 Political?

Table 1.1
Political Reasons

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. POLITICAL INFLUENCE		
3	So, pinahiram kasi talaga ako nung boss ko, ni Cong X sa campaign ni AAA para maging writer niya. And then, after nung manalo siya, kinuha siyang Secretary. And then, ayun, sumunod naging Usec naman niya ako. So, ayun.	My boss, Cong X asked me to support the campaign of AAA to be his writer. And then, after he won, my boss was appointed as Secretary. And then, I became his Undersecretary.
4	I'm working with former Senate President X. So for me, it was a very prestigious and privileged position working with him.	
5	I'm holding a coterminous post... So I started with Chief Justice X. So from Chief Justice X, now I'm with Chief Justice Y... Kasi pag-co-term trust and confidence ng appointing authority.	I'm holding a coterminous post. So I started with Chief Justice X, and now I'm with Chief Justice Y... Because when you're coterminous, it's based on the trust and confidence of the appointing authority.

II. POLITICAL DENIAL		
4	Dati may sinulat akong articles about, ginagawa pa lang yung Mall X noon. Na-interview ko yung isang official ng City Government X and he told me na may mga crack talaga yung Mall X sa likod. So sinulat ko yun pero dineny niya.	I once wrote articles about the construction of Mall X. I interviewed an official from the City Government X, and he told me that there were indeed cracks at the back of Mall X. So, I wrote about it, but he denied it.
III. MEDIA HARASSMENT		
4	So yung editorial namin kinausap ako. So yun yung time na feel ko na parang, mawawalan pa ako ng trabaho dahil nagsulat ka lang ng totoo. So, may libel case din ako. Siyempre, pag may libel case ka, kasama yung editors mo, parang feeling mo napahamak mo sila. Pero okay naman, na-dismiss naman.	Then our editorial team talked to me. That was the time when I felt like I might even lose my job just because I exposed the truth. I also had a libel case. Of course, when a libel case is filed against you, your editors are your co-respondents, and you feel like you've put them in a difficult position. But it turned out okay, the case was dismissed.
IV. REPRESSION DUE TO MEDIA OWNER'S VESTED INTERESTS		
10	I kind of did not agree with some policies in the workplace, so I left.	
10	Sa private media kasi naka-experience na rin talaga ko ng heartbreak dahil there were stories na trinabaho	In private media, I really experienced heartbreak because there were stories that I worked on,

	mo, yun pala they did not go well with...[the media owner] you know...	but it turned out they didn't go well with... [the media owner] you know...
10	Though there are some cases na desk ang papalit ng angulo without informing me, kasi nabangga ang gusto ng owner. May feeling of betrayal kasi the private outlet claims to be objective.	In some cases, the desk would change the news story angle without informing me because my story did not sit well with the media owner. There's a feeling of betrayal because the private outlet claims to be objective.

Table 1.1 discusses the four major political reasons why former media practitioners left their profession to enter the government service. These are Political Influence, Political Denial, Media Harassment, and Biased and Anti-Workers' Workplace Policies.

I. Political Influence: Three respondents (P3, P4, and P5), two of whom are occupying coterminous posts, entered the government service through political influence or their affiliation with the officials in the government. The researcher believes that given the participants' extensive media experience (ranging from seven to 20 years) and exposure to government dealings and processes, political leaders tapped their expertise to be of service to the government.

II. Political Denial: P4, a former print journalist for 10 years, narrated his experience of writing an exposé about a large shopping mall and eventually being denied by his source who happened to be a city government official. The researcher surmises that there are efforts to restrict press freedom and the public's rights of access to information. The press freedom is under threat as shown in the declining support and respect for media autonomy (*Reporters sans frontières* or RSF, "Global Analysis: 2024 World Press Freedom Index – journalism under political pressure," 2024).

III. Media Harassment: P4 experienced harassment for playing his role as a watchdog. He, together with his media company, was slapped with a libel case for publishing an exposé and later, got reprieve from the court by dismissing the case. The World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022 titled "Journalism is a Public Good" showed that journalists are threatened with harassment, imprisonment, violence, or death for doing their jobs (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2021). The researcher supposes that the tradition of watchdog in the country's media remains amid threats and harassments.

IV. Media Repression Due Media Owner’s Vested Interests: P10 got frustrated with some biased and repressive policies in his previous media company. He felt betrayed after the stories he was working on never got published because they were turned down by the media owner. The news story angles were sometimes changed to cater to the interest of the media owners. The researcher posits that media owners’ supposed vested “political and economic interests” caused repression within their organization. The trend of media ownership remains –that “a handful of conglomerates and influential families” have wielding power and influence on news stories that get published to pursue their vested interests (Nuval, 2024). Herman et.al (2023) shared the same concern that the media is being used for political propaganda and the political interests of media owners.

What are the reasons behind the migration of print, broadcast and multimedia journalists to the government service in terms of:

1.2 Economic?

**Table 1.2
Economic Reasons**

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. FINANCIAL SECURITY IN PUBLIC SECTOR		
A. SECURITY OF TENURE		
1	Siyempre, tiningnan mo rin naman, yun, yung Foreign Service, may security of tenure ka.	Of course, you also considered that in the Foreign Service, you have security of tenure.
4	Mas stable yung government. Kasi ang government, habang may tax na kinocollect, di naman nasisira yung government. Nandiyan lang yung government. Unlike yung private companies, pwedeng mag-shutdown, ma-bankrupt, anytime, di ba?	The government is more stable. As long as taxes are being collected, the government won't collapse. The government will always be there. Unlike private companies, they can shut down or go bankrupt at any time, right?

4	Pinaka-stable na trabaho talaga yung sa government. Maganda siya para sa edad ko na ano eh, yung paretire na rin.	Government jobs are the most stable. It's ideal for someone my age who's nearing retirement.
5	Siguro ang best example nito was during the pandemic, na maraming nag-hold up ng mga private organizations. Nung nasa government ka, secured ka eh, regardless of the position.	I think the best example of this was during the pandemic when many private organizations were holding up. But if you are in government, you are secure, regardless of your position.
7	Yung family ko nagsabi na mas stable nga sa government.	My family said that it's indeed more stable in government.
9	Of course, I know that tenure in the government and then yung yung years mo is may value.	Of course, I know that tenure in the government and your years of service have value.
13	I left Print Media Company X at the height of the pandemic and I needed security.	I left Print Media Company X at the height of the pandemic because I needed security.
B. HIGHER COMPENSATION		
3	Siyempre, alam naman natin na mas okay yung sweldo, lalo na sa government. At that time, may position pa, may rank kami, so official kami, so mas mataas talaga yung sweldo.	Of course, we know that the salary is better, especially in government. At that time, I had a position and a rank, so I was an official, and the salary was indeed higher.
4	Compensation really was far [much better] compared to the benefits that we have [had] as journalists.	

5	Kasi (because) the pay is more competitive at least with the [Judiciary].	
7	Feeling ko mas financially stable sa government.	I felt that it was more financially stable in the government.
8	Because the pay wasn't enough. So... and at that time, I wasn't getting any younger. You need something more stable.	I was also seeking better compensation, and yes, better compensation was actually probably the major reason I left the media industry in general.
9	Other [reason] siyempre 'yung compensation.	Another reason, of course, was the compensation.
12	So economic [reason] is yung higher salary.	So, the economic reason was the higher salary.
15	I was also seeking better compensation sana. And yes, better compensation, that's actually like probably the major reason kung bakit po ako umalis ng media industry in general.	I was also seeking better compensation, and yes, better compensation was actually probably the major reason I left the media industry in general.
C. PROVISION OF BENEFITS		
3	Kasi, alam naman natin yung mga benepisyo ng government. Yung lahat, yung mga overtime, nabibigay lahat yun.	Because, as we know, the benefits in government are good. All of them, including overtime, are provided.
3	Ako, sa personal experience ko yan ah, na parang, kumbaga nung nalipat ako sa gobyerno, mas well-compensated, yung mga benepisyo nabibigay, may	Based on my personal experience, when I transferred to the government, I was well-compensated, the benefits were given,

	mga overtime, yung nababayaran nang tama.	overtime was paid properly.
9	Mas maraming benefits. And, of course, there's retirement. I know that there will be a retirement package once I retire. So, compared to the previous company that I worked for, na wala.	There are more benefits. And, of course, there's retirement. I know there will be a retirement package once I retire. So, compared to the previous company I worked for, which had none.
10	Although sa government, particularly sa [Legislative], maayos ang benefits.	Although in the government, particularly in the [Legislative], the benefits are good.
12	I think mas marami rin po benefits sa government compared sa private. And also yung mga scholarship benefits. And then, so, maraming opening for trainings.	I think there are more benefits in government compared to the private sector. Also, there are scholarship benefits. There are many opportunities for training as well.
15	Kasi yung mga former colleagues ko, actually contractual yung ano nila eh, position nila sa government. But, parang na-outweigh talaga ng compensation and benefits yung the fact na they have to be renewed every six months.	Some of my former colleagues were actually in contractual positions in the government, but the compensation and benefits really outweighed the fact that they had to be renewed every six months.
II. FINANCIAL INSECURITY IN MEDIA SECTOR		
A. NO SECURITY OF TENURE		
10	Sa (In) private media, usually there's no clear tenure eh. Sometimes if they want, if they don't want you working for them anymore,	

	somehow, mangyayari 'yan (that will happen).	
11	Walang sense of stability.	There's no sense of stability.
B. LOW COMPENSATION		
3	Yung mababa yung sweldo.	The salary is low.
5	I think it's a fact that salary in the media industry isn't competitive, especially in the newspaper industry. Mababa ang salary ko (My salary is low).	
8	The pay for media work was not enough. So I have to look out for, better opportunities for me to use my skill. So, I opted to work in government after.	
14	I think economic kasi mababa lang ng sahod natin eh. Kasi parang 'yung mga kaklase ko, parang ang tataas na ng mga sahod, tapos parang after 10 years, parang pulubi pa rin ako.	I think it's economic because our salary was low. My classmates seemed to have higher salaries, and after 10 years, I still felt like I was a pauper.
C. LACK OF BENEFITS		
3	Alam naman natin yung condition natin sa media, di ba, na may mga yung, alam naman natin yung mga kwento na walang benepisyo, gaano, di ba?	We all know the conditions in the media, right? We know the stories about how there are hardly any benefits, don't we?
4	Not all media entities, not all media outfit gives yung well-compensated package para	Not all media entities, not all media outfits offer a well-compensated

	sa isang journalist, gaya natin.	package for journalists like us.
9	Kung may, kung na-aksidente, parang wala na [insurance].O wala rin namang hazard pay. Parang wala rin hazard pay, night differential. Wala. Ang meron lang is transportation allowance. Pero sobrang liit lang din naman.	If you have an accident, it's like there's no insurance. There's also no hazard pay, no night differential. None. The only thing provided is transportation allowance, but it's very minimal.
11	I think at that time Broadcast Company X particularly don't have any provisions for media practitioners because of the pandemic. I'm working on field kasi documentaries yung mga hawak ko. So, lumalabas kami, pero parang wala ako makita at the time na parang proper provisions of the Office, number one, for health concerns, for our hazard pays.	I think at that time, Broadcast Company X didn't have any provisions for media practitioners because of the pandemic. I was working in the field because I was handling documentaries. So, we went out, but at that time, I couldn't see any proper provisions from the Office, especially for health concerns and our hazard pay.
11	Masyadong masalimuot yung sa amin kasi may utang pa kami sa kumpanya. Kasi hindi nila kami pinapasahod. Ang rule kasi for airing basis kayo. So, syempre, wala kaming ayuda. So, parang ang ginawa nila, they want us to, pwede kaming, alam mo yun, parang pwede kang mag-cash advance. Ako, I have to cut it down eh. Kasi, yun nga, I'm afraid that, you know, if I wanted to leave, hindi ko siya mabayaran. Parang ganon. So, ako,	Our situation was very complicated because we even had debts to the company. They weren't paying us. The rule was that we were paid based on airing. So, of course, we had no provision of assistance. What they did was allow us to take a cash advance. But I had to cut it down because I was afraid that should I decide to leave, I would not be able to pay them. That's how it was. I was

	nakaalis naman ako, kahit may kulang ako sa kanila.	allowed to leave even if I still owed them money.
12	Compared po sa media, and sa private sector, [yung trainings] parang hindi masyadong ine-encourage, or hindi naman ine-encourage.	Compared to the media and private sector, trainings are not really encouraged or supported.
III. FAMILY NEEDS		
3	I have a family to raise, so yun yung reason din talaga.	I have a family to raise, so that was really another reason.
8	I mean, if you want to start a family after, hindi [salary in media] siya ano eh, hindi siya viable. So, I have to look for a job that would be more suitable to what are my plans.	I mean, if you want to start a family later, [the salary in media] is not viable. So, I had to look for a job that would be more suitable for my plans.
10	But after marriage and having a child, economic also played, also became a factor in leaving my profession as a private media practitioner.	But after getting married and having a child, economics also became a factor in leaving my profession as a private media practitioner.

Table 1.2 presents varied economic reasons why former print, broadcast, and multimedia journalists migrated to the government service. To thresh out the economic difficulties and challenges hounding the news media sector, this study came up with three major themes: (1) Financial Security in the Public Sector, (2) Financial Insecurity in the Media Sector, and (3) Family Needs.

Under “Financial Security in Government” segment, the sub-themes were Security of Tenure, Higher Compensation, and Provision of Benefits. Listed under the “Financial Insecurity in the Media Sector” were No Security of Tenure, Low Compensation, and Lack of Benefits.

I. Financial Security in the Public Sector

A. Security of Tenure: Six (6) participants who are mostly and previously worked as print journalists with age brackets ranging from 29 to 57 years old – P1, P4, P5, P7,

P9, and P13 identified security of tenure as a reason why they jump shipped from the news media sector to the government. The participants believed that the government is providing security of tenure than the private news media sector. This was seen during the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly affected the country's media landscape as observed by P4 and P5. The World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022: *“Journalism is a Public Good,”* stated that the “already shaky” financial fundamentals of the news media industry were hit by the pandemic, which resulted in substantial decline in advertising revenues, job losses or retrenchments, and newsroom closures (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2021).

B. Higher Compensation: Higher, better, and more competitive salary being offered by the government was mentioned as another major factor that attracted former journalists to leave their newsrooms. P3, P4, P5, P7, P8, P9, P12, and P15 did not think twice about leaving their profession because of the government's compensation package. Seven of the respondents came from the print media sector with one (1) to 20 years of media experience. In the World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022, *“Journalism is a Public Good,”* the UNESCO (2021) noted the reduction in global newspaper advertising revenue declined by half in the last five years, and that there was a 13-percent decline in global newspaper circulation between 2019 and 2020, citing the PwC's Global Entertainment and Media Outlook 2021-2025. In its 2023 Digital News Report Philippines, the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism revealed that print media as source of news among Filipinos is “on a steady decline” from 2020 to 2023 (Media Ownership Monitor Philippines 2023, *“Print media: Readership on the decline”*, Vera Files 2023).

C. Provision of Benefits: The government's provision of benefits was identified by P3, P9, P10, P12, and P15 as another reason why they left their profession. Among the benefits cited were overtime pay, retirement package, scholarships, and trainings.

II. Financial Insecurity in the Media Sector

A. No Security of Tenure: The participants from the multimedia and broadcast media sectors who both had extensive media experience mentioned the lack of security of tenure as a reason for leaving the news media industry. P10 and P11 discussed that there is no clear tenure and sense of stability in the private media sector. P10 narrated that they were at the mercy of media owners who have the final say on their fate. Nuval (2024) cited that the media companies are owned by “a handful of conglomerates and influential families.” This year's shutdown of the CNN Philippines that displaced 300 employees showed the financial vulnerability of the country's media sector (Cordero, 2024).

B. Low Compensation: Four participants who belonged to print, broadcast and multimedia sectors and whose ages range from 37 to 50 years old zeroed in on low compensation as the reason behind their transfer to government service. P3, P5, P8, and P14 looked at their low compensation as key reason why they chose to work in the public sector. The National Union of Journalists of the Philippines (2023) sought better pay and

working conditions for all Filipino journalists, citing that their “economic and labor rights are as much press freedom issues” (NUJP Labor Day Statement, “*Solidarity on Labor Day: Media Workers Are Workers Too,*” 2023).

C. Lack of Benefits: The lack of benefits was identified as among the reasons why the participants left their print and broadcast media companies. P3, P4, P9, P11, and P12 looked for the following benefits: insurance, hazard pay, night differential, enough transportation allowance, and healthcare protection. P11, who had a 20-year media stint, specifically lamented their broadcast company’s failure to provide healthcare protection and hazard pays given the risks of actually contracting the virus at the height of COVID-19 pandemic. The survey conducted by the ICFJ and the Tow Center for Digital Journalism at Columbia University showed that 30 percent of the 1,406 journalist-respondents stated no single piece of recommended protective equipment had been supplied to field reporters, and that the risk of actually contracting the virus was among the biggest challenges faced by the journalists (Posetti et.al. 2020). The survey also found that 67 percent of the respondents rated financial concerns “as a significant difficulty.”

III. Family Needs

The participants whose ages range from 43 to 53 years old commonly identified that their quest to start and raise a family prodded them to leave their jobs for government service. P3, P8, and P10 were in unison that they had to find viable and stable source of income for their family.

What are the reasons behind the migration of print, broadcast and multimedia journalists to the government service in terms of:

1.3 Social?

Table 1.3
Social Reasons

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. SERVICE TO COUNTRY		
1	Yung nakikita mo nga, yung opportunities available, yung chance to serve the country in a different capacity.	You are seeing the available opportunities, the chance to serve the country in a different capacity.

7	Syempre, siguro, isa na rin na [reason], sa UP ako nag-aral, so parang ni-rationalize ko na giving back din sa government. Giving back to the Filipino people na pinag-aral naman ako, scholar.	Of course, I guess, one reason is that I studied at UP (University of the Philippines), so I rationalized it as giving back to the government. Giving back to the Filipino people who funded my studies, as a scholar.
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II. SENSE OF MISSION

1	You know, when we go into service, sabi ko nga eh (like I said), it's just like I'm still in the newspaper profession eh, because part of our job is to report, right? It's just like I'm just a reporter, like manning the bureau of the Republic of the Philippines, looking for stories to report, stories about developments that affect the Philippines, stories about how our people are, and then you prepare the report.	
2	So it was really a big sacrifice to shift, or to jump ship from private sector to government.	
4	We really roam around the country to help our under privileged fellow Filipinos.	
7	Ang siguro turning point ko na pwede ko ikwento yung isa sa mga last major stories na na-cover ko, yung na lumubog yung Princess of the Stars. Tapos bumabagyo, bumalik pa ako ng pier, tapos i-interview ako ng mga pami-pamilya na	I guess my turning point was, maybe I can share one of the last major stories I covered—the capsizing of the Princess of the Stars. There was a storm, and I went back to the pier and I interviewed the families—about six

	<p>mga anim sa pamilya nila, nalunod yung mga ganon.</p> <p>Tapos parang iniisip ko, para saan ito lahat? So isusulat ko siya, so? Tapos, ano nang mangyayari? Parang yun yung iniisip ko, ano na? Paano ko makakatulong? Eh, isusulat ko lang naman 'to, tapos nakakaiyak. Tapos, so? Ano nga? Ano nangyari? Ano nangyari sa... Although alam ko napakababaw, no?</p>	<p>of them—whose relatives had drowned.</p> <p>I was thinking, what is all this for? So, I'll write about it, and then what? What will happen? I was thinking, what's next? How can I help? I'm just going to write about this, and it's so heartbreaking. So, what then? What happened? What happened to... Although I know it sounds really trivial, right?</p>
III. SOCIAL INFLUENCE		
1	<p>I first heard about the Foreign Service, at a very young age. I would hear my aunt mentioned embassy, consul general, ambassador, and etc. So alam ko na yung mga terms na yan eh (I was already familiar with those terms). Then in, in high school, I had a friend who told me that her mother worked with the former senator Shahani, that she would want to be a diplomat like her one day. So alam mo yun, nasa radar screen (So you know, it was on my radar screen)... But ano, hindi ko siya masyadong siniseryoso noon (But, I didn't take it too seriously back then). But of course, pumasok yan eventually (I considered it eventually).</p>	

1	Sa (In) Saudi Arabia, I was covering the Consulate, the Philippine Consulate in Jeddah. So the Vice Consul then was telling me that, you know, as a journalist, you have the qualities needed for one to become a diplomat. So, you write well, articulate yourself. So binanggit niya yon (he mentioned it). So he gave me a book, the Foreign Service Code for me to read and see.	
2	Because at that time, what really prompted me to join government was my coverage of the Department of Foreign Affairs when I was asked about the ASEAN Summit in Bali in 2003. And at that time, I had so many questions that no one could answer. So I thought, why am I asking the questions? Maybe I should just pursue the answers myself.	
15	What also prompted me to try sa (working in) government agency is I was influenced also by former colleagues sa (in) Broadsheet X, who made the switch to government agency service.	
IV. WORKING CONDITIONS IN MEDIA SECTOR		
A. SLOW CAREER PROGRESSION		
1	So, this is more on your career change... Parang, if I	So, this is more about your career change... It felt like if I stayed in the

	stay in the newspaper, so I'll be stuck here.	newspaper, I'd be stuck there.
1	So for you to be editor-in-chief, even if I aspire to be one, it's going to take me years.	
9	I decided not to be a reporter anymore because during that time, I was already old enough in the beat and then new reporters are coming in, younger reporters so I just decided to have a career shift.	
B. NO SYSTEM OF MENTORSHIP		
11	So, parang when we are expanding, syempre, yung mga magagaling, nag-expand din yung galing nila to other projects, other programs. So, nawala na yung system of mentorship. Naging, napalitan na lang sya ng raket raket lang yung mga tao.	So, as we expanded, naturally, the talented people also extended their skills to other projects and programs. As a result, the system of mentorship was lost. It was replaced by a situation where people just took on various sideline jobs.
C. DANGEROUS AND RISKY COVERAGES		
4	During 2001, di ba yung EDSA 2, we covered yung ousting of former president Joseph Erap Estrada. So nasa middle kami ng Mendiola noon eh, nung nag-barge yung pro, saka yung nag-ano sila eh, parang collide talaga yung pro and anti-Erap. So, it's very dangerous din.	In 2001, during EDSA 2, we covered the ousting of former President Joseph Erap Estrada. We were in the middle of Mendiola when the pro-Erap groups barged and clashed with anti-Erap groups. It was a very dangerous situation.
4	I also experienced covering 'yung Basilan. 'Yung first	I also experienced covering Basilan during

	Abu Sayyaf hostage-taking incident. I was assigned there. But during that time, nasa Broadsheet X pa ako. So, yung sabi ng editor ko na, mag-cover ka doon for two weeks lang. Tumagal ng isang buwan, di ba? So, yun 'yung mga risky operations.	the first Abu Sayyaf hostage-taking incident. I was assigned there, but at that time, I was still with Broadsheet X. My editor told me to cover it for just two weeks, but it ended up lasting a month. Those were risky operations.
4	Walang ganong clear na ano eh, na agreement [on hazard pay, insurance], wala akong pinirmahan. Basta coverage lang, tawag ng trabaho. Passion. Gano'n naman tayo, di ba? Pag binigyan ka ng assignments, gagawin mo rin. Tsaka during that time, bata ka pa, so very eager ka rin to cover yung mga ganung significant events...Wala kaming pinag-usapan about compensation. Kung anong mangyari sa'yo o insurance, di ba?	There wasn't a clear agreement on things like hazard pay or insurance; I didn't sign anything. It was just coverage, a call of duty. It was all about passion. That's how it is with us, right? When you're given assignments, you do them. Plus, at that time, I was still young and very eager to cover such significant events. We didn't discuss about compensation or any benefits or insurance just in case something happens to me.
D. IRREGULAR WORKING HOURS		
6	Given that our work at Broadsheet X that time was six (6) days a week. We only have 1 rest day. And we, even on rest days or holidays we are on call. So that's why I decided to transfer to a more scheduled occupation	
7	So, medyo nag-take na ang toll yung irregular hours na. Kunyari nung time na umalis ako, medyo may mga mga events non na kahit	So, the irregular hours really started to take a toll. For example, when I left, there were events where you had to go out

	bumabagyo, lalabas ka. Tapos, kahit gabi tatawagan ka...Pati yung mga meeting kasi gabi.	even if it was stormy. And you'd get calls even at night... Plus, meetings were often held in the evening.
7	Galing sa work, pupunta ka pa sa office para mag-attend ng meeting ng gabi. Hindi mo alam hanggang anong oras yun. Siyempre, mga editors, gabi pa sila natatapos. So, hintayin mo yun.	After work, you'd still have to go to the office to attend a meeting at night. You never knew how long it would last. Of course, editors often finished late, so you had to wait for them.
12	Yun din po pala, yung pagpasok, six (6) days per week. So, compared sa government na parang ano lang, 40 hours per week. And then, kapag holidays, holiday talaga. And then, kapag may suspension, suspended din. So, ayun din po. So, naka-contribute din yung mga days off.	Also, working six days a week was another factor. In comparison, government work usually has a 40-hour work week. Plus, holidays are actually observed, and if there's a suspension, it's also enforced. So, the days off were a significant factor as well.
E. MOBILITY		
4	Nag-cocommute tayo, kailangan natin puntahan yung mga event na pumuputok. Pag may sunog, may patayan, kailangan natin puntahan.	We had to commute and needed to go to events where things were happening, like fires or killings.
9	Siguro yung unsafe is dahil wala namang mobility. So, pupunta ka sa coverage na ikaw lang din. Tapos, uuwi ka rin ng ikaw lang din,wala ka namang din sasakyan.	The unsafe part was that there was no mobility support. You'd go to the coverage on your own and then return home alone as well, no vehicle provided for you

F. INTENSE WORKLOAD/UNCLEAR WORK DELINEATION		
4	Ang dami nating beat. And then, ang lawak nung kino-cover natin. Ako yung buong South. So, ilang cities meron sa South. Makati, Taguig, Paranaque, Pasay, Muntinlupa, Las Piñas, Pateros.	We had a lot of beats to cover, and the areas we covered were vast. I was responsible for the entire South. So, that included several cities: Makati, Taguig, Parañaque, Pasay, Muntinlupa, Las Piñas, and Pateros.
11	Binubugbog ako sa trabaho...I was trained to exert all of my efforts di ba?. Lahat kasi doon, parang, money mo, physical mo, lahat. Lahat ang pwede mo ibigay, di ba?	I am really trained to handle intense workload ... I was trained to put in all of my effort, right? Everything there was about giving it all—your money, your physical effort, everything. You gave all that you could, right?
13	To be honest po, parang nawalan po ng boundary kasi since we're all working at home and as a media, as a journalist, we work literally 24/7. So, natanggalan po ng boundary ang work and life	To be honest, it felt like there was no boundary anymore because, since we're all working from home and as a media, as a journalist, we work literally 24/7. So, the boundary between work and life disappeared.
15	Sa akin po kasi, I also parang dumating din ako sa point na I wanted clear delineation ng work and personal time. So, I'm pretty sure you understand this na parang kahit na siguro patulog ka na tapos biglang may nag may nag-break na balita, kailangan mong bumangon and you have to work. So parang it's okay for the first few years pero parang you realize then later on na parang mapaisip ka if	For me, I also reached a point where I wanted a clear separation between work and personal time. I'm pretty sure you understand this feeling—where even if you're about to sleep and suddenly there's breaking news, you have to get up and work. It's manageable for the first few years, but then you start to question if this is

	this is something that you can do in the longer run.	something you can sustain in the long run.
V. DYING PRINT MEDIA		
7	Although nung pag-alis ko hindi pa naman ganon ka grabe yung kunwari, effect ng social media sa ano sa newspaper industry. Pero ngayon, super apparent na yun. Pero yun, yung isa ko naisip nung time na yun kasi medyo looming na siya na.	Although when I left, the impact of social media on the newspaper industry wasn't yet that severe. But now, it's become very apparent. That time, it was one of the things crossed my mind, that there was a looming [crisis].
7	So, nung time na yun kasi may looming na parang problem or challenge sa media industry na newspapers are dying parang ganon, so nung time na yun pa, what, 2007 ganon? So may ganon na. So, parang inisip ko, super, super ano eh, parang medyo nakaka-stress din yung isipin yung hindi mo alam kung ano na yung next sa... Ngayon, wala na ng Metro Page, di ba?	So, at that time, there was already a looming problem or challenge in the newspaper media industry, like it was dying. This was around 2007, if I recall correctly. It was already becoming apparent. I thought about how stressful it was not knowing what the future would hold. Now, there's no more Metro Page, right?
VI. MEDIA CORRUPTION		
1	Siyempre meron pa rin mga bumabangat na dyan, yung mga ACDC (attack-collect-defend-collect) na mga kasama natin. Kung mayaman lang ako, I want to have a broadsheet for Central Luzon. Train young journalists. Pay them well. Pay them well. Para hindi sila ma-tempt dun sa tumanggap.	Of course, there are still those who criticize, our colleagues in the media who are the ACDC (attack-collect-defend-collect) type. If I were rich, I would want to have a broadsheet for Central Luzon. I would train young journalists and pay them well—pay them well—so they

		wouldn't be tempted to accept bribes.
5	It's a fact din naman, merong developmental journalism. It's something na hindi ko siya ma-take. So, sabi ko, rather than engage in that, you might as well, hanap ka na lang na mas malaki yung sweldo, di ba? I mean, you have to earn your keep, you have to earn your salary. So, para maging effective ka muna, kailangan you have integrity.	It's also a fact that there is developmental journalism, which I find unacceptable. So, I said to myself, rather than engage in that, you might as well look for a job with a higher salary, right? I mean, you have to earn your keep and your salary. To be effective, you need to have integrity first.
VII. MORE TIME WITH FAMILY		
4	I mean, the government we, especially in the [Legislative], we work Monday to Thursday. So you have three days for your family. That's quite convenient for us and spending quality time with my family is one of the most very important things for me as a father, as a husband. Because sometimes if you are a journalist, you cover during weekend, holiday, rainy seasons, typhoon like this, so parang limited yung family time (so family time is quite limited).	
6	At that time, I was newly married and had just given birth. So, I wanted an 8-to-5 job. So that's mainly my motivation, that was my main motivation for transferring to government office.	

7	Inisip ko, siguro, family, yung gano'n na parang ano na next step ko? Paano na 'to?.. Sa media kasi medyo...may priority ka na hindi pamilya mo. Although, meron din naman kaya nila pamilya, pero parang hindi ko kaya eh. Wala akong energy sa ganon	Maybe, I was thinking of my family. So, I was figuring out what my next step should be. In media, you often have priorities and that don't include your family. Although some people manage to balance family life that I couldn't handle. I didn't have the energy for that.
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Table 1.3 indicates diverse social reasons why former journalists from print, broadcast, and multimedia companies decided to work for the government. To dig deeper into the social reasons that prodded the participants to leave their profession, this study came up with three major themes: (1) Service to Country, (2) Sense of Mission, (3) Social Influence, (4) Working Conditions in Media Sector, (5) Dying Print Media, and More Time with Family.

The participants exhaustively narrated their experiences on “Working Conditions in Media” segment that allowed the researcher to create the following sub-themes: Slow Career Progression, No System of Mentorship; Dangerous and Risky Coverages; Irregular Working Hours, Mobility, and Intense Workload/Unclear Work Delineation.

I. Service to Country: The participants, namely P1 and P7 who were an activist, and a government scholar, respectively expressed their patriotic fervor, mentioning that service to country as their reason to serve the government.

II. Sense of Mission: The participants’ sense of mission was commonly identified as a reason behind the migration to government service. Making a big sacrifice to make a difference, doing their job dutifully for the interest of the country, and helping their fellow compatriots were mentioned by P1, P2, P4, and P7. Holliday (2021) tagged journalism as “a power-replicating machine” – meaning “without a driving mission”, it is guided by profit and, often, power.

III. Social Influence: The participants’ involvement in significant national and foreign coverages influenced them to join the government. P1, and P2, who are holding Executive positions, narrated that their exposure to government officials and their kins, and their immersion stint in their respective beats prepared them to be part of government’s working force. P15 even cited that her former colleagues in Broadsheet X who joined the public sector convinced her to join the government service.

IV. Working Conditions in Media Sector

A. Slow Career Progression: The participants from print media sector identified the slow career progression in the news media sector. P1, a veteran editor and now an experienced government official, and P9 who had 13-year stint in a daily broadsheet realized the need to change their career because of slow career movement in their respective news outfits.

B. No System of Mentorship: P11, an experienced journalist from the broadcast media, identified the absence of mentorship as among the reasons why she left the industry. P11 narrated that given the changing media landscape due to digital technology developments and the journalists' need to be financially secure, the system of mentorship was not prioritized.

C. Dangerous and Risky Coverages: P4, a male print journalist, narrated his experience of covering dangerous and risky national events, including the ouster of former President Joseph Estrada and the Abu Syyaf hostage-taking incident in Basilan as among the reasons why he chose to shift from dangerous and risky coverages to government service, realizing that he was sent on a dangerous mission without any security blanket in terms of hazard pay, insurance, and any form of compensation in case of death or injury. In its World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022, "*Journalism is a Public Good*," the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2021) said journalism continues to be a "deadly" and "dangerous profession." In 2023, at least 120 journalists and media workers, 68 of whom were involved in the Gaza conflict, lost their lives (International Federation of Journalists, 2023). Based on the UNESCO Observatory of Killed Journalists, print journalists are the second most attacked group (22 percent) (International Federation of Journalists, 2023).

D. Irregular Working Hours: The irregular working hours was factored in by P6, P7, and P12 for leaving their print media companies as the government offered a work schedule that allows more personal and family time. In a statement issued on Labor Day, the National Union of Journalists of the Philippines (2023) pushed for better pay and working conditions for all Filipino journalists, citing that their "economic and labor rights are as much press freedom issues." The journalists' union lamented that media companies do not provide overtime, holiday and night differential pay to compensate the long hours of work being rendered by many journalists, and added that when disasters or calamities strike, many journalists "cover without hazard pay or insurance" (NUJP Labor Day Statement, "*Solidarity on Labor Day: Media Workers Are Workers Too*," 2023).

E. Mobility: P4 and P9 from the print sector who had 10 to 13 years of media service mentioned mobility as a safety concern. This is an issue, particularly when the journalists are asked to cover disasters or calamities, and other risky coverages without hazard pay or insurance (National Union of Journalists of the Philippines, 2023)

F. Intense Work Load/ Unclear Work Delineation: The participants who are mostly female, and were from broadcast and print news sector mentioned their intense work load or unclear work delineation as a reason for leaving their respective media

companies. P11, 13, and P15 who spent four to 20 years in the media industry left their profession during the COVID-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, P4, a print journalist for 10 years, stated that even before the pandemic, journalists were given heavy workload.

V. Dying Print Media

P7, a former print media journalist, discussed that the impending death of the print media made her think to change her profession. At the time when she departed the industry, the influence of the digital technology and social media was not that apparent. In the Philippines, the Filipinos' support for print media as news source has been declining from 2020 to 2023, according to the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism's 2023 Digital News Report Philippines (Media Ownership Monitor Philippines 2023, "*Print media: Readership on the decline*", Vera Files 2023). The 2023 Digital News Report Philippines cited that the most popular sources of news in the Philippines are online and social media, while for those who don't access to digital technology, TV and radio news remain important (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2023).

VI. Media Corruption

Two participants who had extensive media experience mentioned that corruption in media exists in the country. P1 and P5 identified envelopmental journalism and ACDC (attack-collect-defend-collect) journalism as forms of media bribery that have been hounding the media industry. Due to low salaries, some of their colleagues succumbed to bribery.

VII. More Time with Family

Participants from the print media mentioned the work schedule in the government that allowed them to spend more time with their family as a reason behind their transfer. P4, P6, and P7 commonly identified the fixed work schedule in the government as more appealing than the erratic schedule in the media sector.

What are the reasons behind the migration of print, broadcast and multimedia journalists to the government service in terms of :

1.4 Personal?

Table 1.4
Personal Reasons

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. CHANGE IN ENVIRONMENT		
1	So, parang, hindi naman na-bored or something, but I felt I needed a change in an environment	So, it wasn't really about being bored or anything, but I felt I needed a change in environment.
9	I left the publishing for personal reasons because during that time, I just realized that I don't want to be a reporter anymore. I want to try to work in government. Because I have been in the private industry for a very long time like actually 20 years na kung idadagdag pa yung mga previous work experiences (if you add up my previous work experiences).	
II. PERSONAL/PROFESSIONAL GROWTH		
1	It's more on your personal advancement. Yung challenge kasi they were telling me, the Foreign Service Officers Exam is one of the hardest, if not the hardest, in the Civil Service. Malaki yung casualty rate dyan. And there were about,	It's more on your personal advancement. The challenge was, they were telling me that the Foreign Service Officers Exam is one of the hardest, if not the hardest, in the Civil Service. The casualty

	I think, if I'm not mistaken, 1,500 of us who took it. And only more or less 20 passed. So mataas yung casualty rate. So even, sabi, even lawyers sometimes fail.	rate is quite high. There were about 1,500 of us who took it, and only around 20 passed. So, the casualty rate is high. Even lawyers sometimes fail.
1	Of course, yung opportunities to see the world. Yung i-expand yung ano mo talaga eh, yung horizon mo.	Of course, there are the opportunities to see the world and truly expand your horizons.
2	I didn't even know FSOs (Foreign Service Officers) become ambassador, so it wasn't really the motivation that I will become an ambassador one day. It was just, just really all about the answers to those global and regional questions that I had that I couldn't find answers to, whether school or in the media. Because you know, government officials will not really tell us the real story right.	
4	I was with him (Senate President X) for 14 years. So, it was a privilege and honor. And I learned many things from Senator X, not just professionally but in my own personal life. I gained many wisdom.	
12	And then personal is, I think personal growth din po. And then, kasi mas interested din po ako sa research, and technical, yung mga policy reviews po	And then, personally, I think another reason was also personal growth. I was also more interested in research and technical aspects, such as policy reviews.

III. JOB BURNOUT/HEALTH		
7	Ayun, isa palang [factor], health din, kasi may asthma ako...Pero syempre love ko naman yung work, pero, syempre, meron ka rin ano sa, premium sa health mo, sa sarili mo.	Also, health was a factor because I have asthma... Of course, I love my work, but you also have to prioritize your health and well-being.
7	Tapos, siyempre, yung news hanggang ilang, ano yun, ilang versions yun. Depende pa kung developing story. So, nung time na yun, parang medyo na-burnout ako.	And then, of course, the news can go through several versions, depending on whether it's a developing story. During that time, I felt somewhat burned out.
11	Tapos siguro, mentally, ano talaga siya eh, it's mentally draining. Sabi ko nga, ano siya eh, it's a kind of job that you are physically drained and mentally drained. Alam mo yun, tawag nito, hindi ka matutulog, hindi ka, alam mo yun, wala kang oras ng kain.	And then, mentally, it's really draining. I've said before that it's a kind of job where you are both physically and mentally exhausted. You know, you don't get to sleep, you don't have time to eat...
13	Also, personal things were taking toll on my mental health... Natanggalan po ng boundary ang work and life. So, it affected my mental health. I burned out. Basically, I got tired of doing what I used to love to do.	Also, personal things were taking a toll on my mental health. The boundary between work and life disappeared, which affected my mental health. I burned out. Basically, I got tired of doing what I used to love.
15	Sabi ko, parang kailangan ko talaga ng personal time para makapagtrabaho nang mas maayos. So yun yung reason kaya medyo personal din kung bakit ako naconvince umalis sa media. Sobrang amplified	I said to myself that I really needed personal time in order to work more effectively. So that was one of the personal reasons that convinced me to leave the media. It was greatly amplified

	syempre nung pandemic kasi bilang isolated ka nanga at home, parang mas naging mahirap to set that boundary na.	during the pandemic because, being isolated at home, it became even harder to set that boundary.
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Table 1.4 shows three major personal reasons why former print, broadcast, and multimedia journalists left their profession for government service. These are Change in Environment, Personal/Professional Growth, and Job Burnout/Health.

I. Change in Environment: P1 and P9 who belong to the print sector identified a change in environment as reason for leaving the industry amid their 13 to 15 years of media experience.

II. Personal/Professional Growth: The participants who belonged to print and broadcast media sectors mentioned their pursuit of personal advancement and professional growth as a reason for career shift. P1, P2, P4 and P12 whose ages range from 25 to 57 years old mentioned that they wanted to expand their horizon, to grow personally and professionally, and to engage in research and policy reviews.

III. Job Burnout/Health: Job burnout or health has been identified as a personal reason by P7, P11, and P13 why they had to leave their profession. Two of these participants who experienced burnout left their job during the COVID-19 pandemic. P7, P11, and P13 are female and served as media practitioners for six (6) to 20 years. Based on the survey conducted by the ICFJ and the Tow Center for Digital Journalism at Columbia University, 70 percent of the 1,406 journalist-respondents indicated that dealing with the mental health impacts of covering the pandemic were the most difficult aspect of their work (Posetti et.al. 2020). The survey also found that 62 percent of the respondents rated assistance with managing mental health and well-being as an important or very important need.

II. The Participants' Roles in their Respective Agencies

What are the roles of former media practitioners in their respective agencies?

Table 2

Former Media Practitioners' Roles in Government Service

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. COMMUNICATIONS		
A. PUBLIC INFORMATION		
1	We need to keep the people informed. We need to keep them inspired. We need to keep them interested. And we need to keep them engaged. So, you can only get them engaged if they're well informed... Inform the people about the good things that our government has been doing.	
2	I'm tasked to do the messaging or to do the press release.	
3	Ako na rin yung gumagawa ng mga press releases ni Cong X.	I am also preparing the press releases for Cong X.
4	Kami gumagawa ng mga captions, press releases ng lahat ng events ng mga senators. Nag-eedit din, proofreading everything, communications dumadaan sa amin. So pinu-proofreading namin lahat. Mga materials, anything related for communications, whether yung press	We handle creating captions and press releases for all the events of the senators. We also edit and proofread everything; all communications pass through us. We proofread all materials, whether it's press releases or other

	releases o yung ginagawang mga materials gaya ng brochures, yung mga mementos, yung mga booklet namin, dumadaan sa amin yan.	communication materials such as brochures, mementos, and booklets. Everything related to communications goes through us.
5	Aside from liaising with the media, I write press releases, and I also edit press releases. Syempre (Of course) when you write, you also cover. So, I'm also in the field from time to time. As I've said, during the Typhoon Carina, I was in the Iloilo to cover the Ethics Summit.	
8	I had the information group, so I managed the development, deployment, and evaluation of the various communication requirements of the Council.	
9	My roles are preparing and disseminating press releases, advisories, information materials to the members of the press.	
10	And then I also write news releases for the senator.	
13	I craft text for our social media contents. This includes photo captions. Basically, those serve as our daily press releases. Also, scripts for audio-visual presentations and social media reels, our art card write-ups, also news monitoring.	

14	Nagsusulat ako press releases, nagsusulat ako ng captions sa social media.	I am writing press releases and captions for social media.
15	[I am] in-charge ng external comms actually. So basically, most of what goes out to the public po, things like press releases, official statements, public advisories, social media posts, talking points ng officials ko.	
B. MEDIA/ PUBLIC RELATIONS		
3	Yung media relations, siyempre, nagagamit ko yun kasi alam naman natin sa Congress, lahat ng mga media doon, halos kaibigan naman natin. Siyempre, ako yung head ng staff niya, ako yung nag-a-arrange sa mga appointments niya (Congressman X).	In media relations, I make use of my connections since we know that in Congress, most of the media there are like friends. As the head of his staff, I am the one who arranges Congressman X's appointments.
5	I liaise with the media. So, when the [Judiciary] needs to contact the media, I am on top of that.	
6	[I'm] liaising with partners on possible projects or programs for our OFWs.	
8	So medyo varied [ang roles] (So, my roles are quite varied). So, it includes events management, media management, public relations, social media management, crisis communication.	
10	Under Office of Senator X, I work in media relations. So,	

	my work would include monitoring news issues. Pag madaling araw pa lang (Early in the morning), I have to send possible issues that might interest the senator. And then, if needed, I also help arrange and transcribe in interviews with Senate media.	
11	I handle media relations.	
14	Aside from that, mga minor roles include yung pag-shepherd ng mga tao, media relations, news monitoring, ganyan. So, more on public relations job.	Aside from that, minor roles include shepherding people, media relations, and news monitoring. So, it's more focused on public relations work.
15	Things like press releases, social media cards, talking points ng mga officials ng government agencies, yun yung mga materials, yun yung mga usual deliverables ko.	Things like press releases, social media cards, and talking points for government officials—these are the materials and usual deliverables I handle.
II. PUBLIC AND CULTURAL DIPLOMACY		
A. PROMOTION OF OFWS' WELFARE AND PROTECTION		
1	So, it's mostly providing consular services to our kababayan, looking after their welfare, extending assistance to those in distress, yung promoting Philippine culture, promoting the Philippines as a tourism and investment destination.	
6	I was assigned to assist the Secretary in special projects on reintegration of [OFWs] and coordinating activities	

	related to the reintegration of OFWs.	
B. PROMOTION OF BILATERAL RELATIONS		
2	I'm really handling the bilateral relations between the Philippines and the United States.	
III. PROGRAM/PROJECT MANAGEMENT		
7	So, parang manager, supervisor ng team. Parang ano ka na team lead ka. So, may mga team ng younger staff na may particular na work streams.	So, it is like a manager or supervisor of a team. You are essentially a team leader. You have teams of younger staff with specific work streams.
9	And then, I also monitor and supervise the operations of the digital media group which handles the agency's social media pages.	
10	Sa project management po, we manage projects that related to science communication, yung pinapondohan ng government...	In project management, we manage projects related to science communication that are funded by the government.
IV. EVENTS MANAGEMENT		
8	So medyo varied [ang roles]. So, it includes events management.	So, the roles are quite varied. They include events management.
10	I'm also an events specialist kasi (because) I handle different events.	
13	Also, our unit po is being tapped, as minsan, as the	Also, our unit is sometimes tapped as

	creative team for the [Legislative's] activities and events.	the creative team for the [Legislative's] activities and events.
V. SUBSTANTIVE POLICY WORK		
2	I was more into the substantive policy [work] because that's what I've always handled since I started in the [Executive agency].	
3	Involved din ako sa paggawa ng legislation, ng mga bills, resolutions, and other functions ni Congressman. So basically yun, ako yung kumbaga, head ng support ni Congressman X.	I'm also involved in drafting legislation, bills, resolutions, and other functions for Congressman X. So basically, I'm the head of Congressman X's support team.
VI. RESEARCH/STUDIES		
8	We also handle the science communication research and development portfolio of the Department, wherein we provide funds for both government and private institutions who would like to do R&D, Research and Development on science communication.	
12	And we also conduct po studies related to the public sector reform.	
VII. CRISIS MANAGEMENT		
8	So medyo varied [ang roles] (The roles are quite varied). So, it includes crisis communication.	

13	And also, sometimes we do crisis management po for the Senate pag necessary (when necessary).	
VIII. OTHER SIGNIFICANT ROLES		
A. ADMINISTRATIVE WORK		
2	Before when I came in, in 2018, I was asked to handle administration, which I really hated because I didn't, I had no idea what admin work is or it's not something that I was interested in.	
B. POLICY/PROGRAM/PROJECT REVIEW		
12	So, we're in charge of policy reviews, policy recommendations on anything related to the governance sector po. So, for example, yung mga (those) related to e-governance, on public accountability, and enhancing government capabilities.	
12	And then we also evaluate and review yung programs and projects relating to civil service and improving service delivery.	And then we also evaluate and review programs and projects related to civil service and improving service delivery.
C. PLANNING		
6	So, in the Planning Office, we support the Secretary directly on plans, on crafting the planning tools of the entire agency.	

D. PUBLIC CONCERNS AND RESPONSE MANAGEMENT		
9	I am also tasked to monitor the operations of the public, and complaints that we receive. So that's, yeah, we receive from other agencies and the public as well through the social media. And then kami yung nagpa-facilitate. So, yung unit na yun is public concerns and response management unit.	I am also tasked with monitoring the operations related to public complaints that we receive. We handle complaints coming from other agencies and the public through social media, and we facilitate the responses. So, the unit I work with is the Public Concerns and Response Management Unit.

Table 2 tackles the wide-ranging roles of the participants in their respective government agencies. Of the 15 participants, 13 of them (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P8, P9, P10, P11, P13, P14, and P15) are into communications. These participants who are working in agencies under the Executive, Legislative, and Judiciary are all involved in the delivery of public information services.

Next to public information services, media and public relations becomes the second major role of the participants in their government agencies, with eight participants (P3, P5, P6, P8, P10, P11, P14, and P15) playing such part.

The researcher posits that the mandate of their respective agencies has something to do with the participants' roles in government service.

Three participants (P1, P2, and P6) are involved in the public and cultural diplomacy, which include the promotion of welfare and protection of Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs), and the promotion of country's bilateral relations. They work in agencies under the Executive branch.

Public and cultural diplomacy, program or project management (P7, P9, and P11), and events management (P4, P11, and P13) are found to be the third major roles of the participants.

While, those participants who are working in agencies under the Executive and Legislative are into substantive policy work (P2 and P3); and are also engaged in crisis communication/ management (P8 and P13).

Other significant roles of the participants include: administrative work, policy/program/project review, planning, and public concerns and response management.

The researcher believes that given their crucial roles in the government service, the participants are still keeping their watchdog roles. Journalism promotes a healthy civic space by providing trusted and fact-based information which is essential to people's participation in a free and open society (Highlights of the World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022, "Journalism is a Public Good", United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2021). Herman et.al (2023) cited the crucial roles of journalists to bridge the communication between the government and the public. They stressed that the fourth estate should always be on board in public decision or policy-making.

III. The Participants' Perceptions about Public Service Delivery

What are the perceptions of former media practitioners about public service delivery?

Table 3
Perceptions about Public Service Delivery

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. COMMITMENT TO PUBLIC TRUST		
2	I don't know if that's unique to me as a former media, but apparently not everyone shares that view or that belief that you have to be competent, you have to be professional, you have to deliver.	
3	Nung napunta ako sa [Agency X], don ko nakita yung pinaka most dedicated, most truthful na mga tao, na nagtatrabaho talaga para sa publiko, para sa gobyerno.	When I was appointed to work at [Agency X], I met the most dedicated, most truthful people, who really work for the public, for the government.
9	So, ngayon, being in the public information, feeling	Now, being in the public information, I feel that I

	<p>ko, mas parang sa akin, mas may accountability sa part ko na eto, part ka na, dapat ikaw yung isa sa mga talagang nagpu-push na talagang makapagbigay talaga ng quality service to the people. So even yung time, kahit weekends, yung para sa bayan. Yun na lang din yung motivation. Motivation ko sa sarili ko, para sa bayan to eh.</p>	<p>have more accountability, especially now I am part of the government, I should be one of those who must really push to provide quality service to the people. Even during weekends, I work for the love of country. That's my motivation—serving the country.</p>
11	<p>I still believe with the importance of ethics. Whatever it is, whether you are in the public service or you are a media practitioner, ethics is very important. Tapos (Then), I also believe that, you know, public service is a public trust; in every, any case, people should trust you whether you are in the, nasa pinaka mababa ka or pinaka mataas (are occupying the lowest or highest position). I'm always on the lookout.</p>	
13	<p>We as public servants should serve people the way we as taong bayans want to be served din. Although now I understand po na may mga bureaucracy or hierarchy po na kailangan sundan. And sometimes it gets frustrating because we tried. Pero, I, personally po, I have the standard na, everything I do or write or produce should be excellent, and if not the best.</p>	<p>We, as public servants, should serve people the way we as citizens would want to be served. Although I understand now that there are bureaucratic or hierarchical processes that need to be followed, which can sometimes be frustrating. However, personally, I maintain the standard that everything I do, write, or produce</p>

		should be excellent, if not the best.
II. PUBLIC SERVICE DELIVERY: A PRIORITY		
1	We're in government, so this [public service delivery] should always be a priority, especially for us in the [Agency X] and the other agencies that also get to work with us overseas.	
2	And because your salaries come from the kaban ng bayan (the nation's coffers), it's not from the private sector, then you shouldn't take it lightly. You should take your work seriously.	
3	Mas maraming populasyon na matandang dalaga sa [Agency X] kasi ganon sila kadedicated sa trabaho nila. Nakalimutan na nila yung sarili nila, yung love life nila para lang sa public service.	There are more single women in the [Agency X] because they are so dedicated to their work. They have forgotten about their own personal life and love life just because of public service.
9	Public service delivery, it must be delivered talaga (really), on point, immediately and then accurately promptly, completely.	
13	Filipinos should get the best service per se from the government.	
III. NEGATIVE TO POSITIVE PERCEPTION		
1	I tell people, you know, when I was a journalist, I was among those criticizing [Agency X]. But you know,	

	when I joined the [Agency X], I saw they've been doing a lot, but they just would not share the story. Not because they don't want to share it, but because they don't have the people who would be able to do the stories for them	
3	Kasi yung, nung nasa media pa lang tayo, lagi yung nakatatak sa atin eh, na government, marumi yan, corrupt yan. Pero nung nakapasok ako sa [Agency X], dun ko nakita andami talagang handang tumulong. Talagang hindi natutulog, hindi umuwi ng bahay para mag-serbisyo sa bayan. Hindi na nakaka-uwi sa pamilya nila para lang tumulong sa bayan kapag may mga sakuna. Honestly, doon talaga na iba yung pagtingin ko sa gobyerno.	When we were in the media, we always had the impression that the government was dirty and corrupt. But when I joined the [Agency X], I saw that there were many people who were genuinely willing to help. They were not able to sleep nor go home just serve the public. They were no longer able to go home just to help during disasters. Honestly, that's when my perception on the government changed.
6	In terms of perception, nagbago, definitely. Kasi nga sabi ko nga, from an 8 to 5 job, akala ko walang ginagawa in the government office. I was proven wrong. I found out na maraming ginagawa and maraming inaayos sa government office.	In terms of perception, it has definitely changed. As I said, from an 8-to-5 job, I used to think that there is no work pressure in government offices. I was proven wrong. I found out that there is a lot of work and that there are many concerns being addressed by the government offices.
15	Nung nasa media kasi ako, I was always critical of the government, actually. In fact, nung college ako, I	When I was in the media, I was always critical of the government. In fact, when I was in college, I

	<p>never imagined working sa government service. Kasi nga, parang when I think of the government, I think of mabagal, I think of inefficient, I think of hindi ganon makatao... But for me, nung pumasok din ako sa government survey, like I said kanina, hindi, hindi nag bago yung view ko sa government.</p> <p>In fact, yung initial view ko of public service was only reinforced when I entered the government service.</p> <p>Nasimula ko na kasing maintindihan, makita yung inner work sa gobyerno. So, feeling ko valid naman yung ibang mga reason kung bakit mabagal.</p>	<p>never imagined working in government service. I thought of the government as slow, inefficient, and lacking in compassion. However, when I joined government service, as I mentioned earlier, my view of the government didn't change. In fact, my initial view of public service was only reinforced when I entered government service. I began to understand and see the inner workings of the government, so I feel that some of the reasons for the perceived slowness are valid.</p>
IV. PUBLIC SERVICE IS INFORMATION DELIVERY		
4	<p>So, one of the basic public services na ginagawa namin is to give yung public, yung precise and accurate information about the institutions. We should inform the public for them to have informed decisions pagdating ng araw, pagdating ng elections, sino ba yung iboboto nila.</p>	<p>One of the basic public services we provide is to give the public precise and accurate information about the institutions. We should inform the public so they can make informed decisions when elections come and choose who to vote for.</p>
5	<p>Pagdating sa (When it comes to) public service delivery, when you're a former practitioner you know what the people needs to hear about, read about. They need to learn about the institution. So basically,</p>	

	pagdating sa Judiciary (with the Judiciary), syempre (of course), since it's the third branch of the government and its primary function is to deliberate cases, mostly, ang dapat na delivery service na ineexpect (the expected service delivery) is to disseminate information about the court's decision.	
10	From my experience po, I view public service in government as similar to that in private media in the sense na, both want to inform the public in a timely and accurate and professional manner. Also in both cases, we also have to keep in mind yung (the) views and positions ng (of the) principal.	
14	I think, pag meron kang background kasi sa media, you are able to understand the dynamics of how you pass information...May times kasi, ang problema is yung public relations mismo na nagsimula sa government, hindi nila alam yung dynamics sa loob ng media. So, with experience sa media, galing ka sa media, papasok ka sa public relations ng government, you're able to, hindi naman perfectly, but rather, you are able to communicate efficiently.	I think having a media background helps you understand the dynamics of how information is delivered. There are times that the problem is public relations that started with government because they don't the dynamics within the media. So, with your media experience, when you eventually handle public relations in government, you are able to communicate more efficiently, if not perfectly.
V. CONTINUED QUEST FOR TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY		

8	Yung lens mo as a journalist does not really go away. You still seek for transparency and accountability when you're working in the government. Kahit na may inis ka over red tape, and seemingly circuitous processes in government, yun yung nadadala mo from media practice. Yun ding balanced view mo of the world na... and your bias for the truth and for the people that you serve.	Your lens [perspective] as a journalist doesn't really go away. You still seek transparency and accountability when working in government. Even though you may get frustrated with red tape and seemingly circuitous processes in government, that's something you keep from your media practice. As well as your balanced view of the world and your bias for the truth and for the people you serve.
12	I think meron naman pong mga efforts to enhance transparency and accountability...Overall po, may mga accomplishments naman but more work still needs to be done to enhance yung transparency and government efficiency.	I think there are efforts to enhance transparency and accountability...Overall, there have been accomplishments, but more work still needs to be done to improve transparency and government efficiency.
VI. BRINGING GOVERNMENT CLOSER TO PEOPLE		
7	Dito sa government, kunyari, mag-lelead ka ng team na nagpu-push ng ganitong [financial inclusion] tapos makikita mo nagwo-work together. Yung parang sa policy change, basta mas apparent. Mas naco-connect ko siya sa, natutunan ko sa school before, tapos yung family values din, parang yung pagtulong, parang diretso. So kunyari yung financial inclusion or bringing	In government, for example, when you lead a team pushing for something like financial inclusion, and you see everyone working together, it becomes more apparent. The policy change is much more apparent. I can connect it better with what I learned in school and also with family values, like helping others directly. For

	[Agency X] closer to the people.	instance, financial inclusion or bringing the [Agency X] closer to the people.
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Table 4 tackles the perceptions of the participants about public service delivery. These perceptions were clustered into six major themes: (1) Commitment to Public Trust, (2) Public Service Delivery: A Priority, (3) Negative to Positive Perception; (4) Public Service is Information Delivery; (5) Continued Quest for Transparency and Accountability; and (6) Bringing Government Closer to People.

I. Commitment to Public Trust: The participants who had a media stint of 6 to 20 years believed that public servants should exemplify professionalism, competence, ethics, dedication and commitment to public trust when it comes to public service delivery. For P2, P3, P9, P11, P13 who were from broadcast, print and multimedia sectors, public service is a public trust.

II. Public Service Delivery: A Priority: The participants were in consensus that the delivery of public service must be prioritized at all costs. P1, P2, P3, P9, and P13 stressed the importance of having an efficient, prompt, and complete delivery of public service.

III. Negative to Positive Perception: The participants narrated how their negative perception about government was changed or how their initial view of government service was reinforced when they entered the government service. P1, P3, P6, and P15 stated that their immersion in their respective agencies that are actively involved in public service delivery made them realize that those in the government have been doing a lot in spirit of genuine service and for love of country.

IV. Public Service is Information Delivery: Providing accurate, credible and precise information in an efficient, timely and professional manner is a form of public service delivery. This was commonly identified by P4, P5, P10, and P14 as their perception about public service delivery. The four participants previously worked as multimedia and print journalists, and their current roles in their respective agencies are into public information services and media relations. As a tool, information empowers people to exercise their basic rights, permits for citizen’s participation and public trust in democratic governance and sustainable development (Windhoek+30 Declaration: “Information as a Public Good” issued during the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization World Press Freedom Day Global Conference on 29 April to 3 May 2021 in Windhoek, Namibia). The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2021) stressed that the delivery of trusted and fact-based information is vital to people’s participation in a free and open society (Highlights of the World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022, “Journalism is a Public Good”).

V. Continued Quest for Transparency and Accountability: The participants from print media sector pointed out that the continued quest for transparency and accountability in the delivery of public service remains. P8 and P12 believed that more work still needs to be done to enhance transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy. In its Editorial, the Philippine Daily Inquirer (2023) challenged President Marcos Jr. “to reverse” the supposed reduced adherence to transparency and good governance by his predecessor by directing the government institutions to “deepen their commitment to freedom of information (FOI) principles.” Citing a Philippine Center for Investigative Journalism (PCIJ) 2022 report, the PDI said the approval of FOI requests only stood at 40 percent, which was only half of its 80-percent approval rate target (Editorial: Strengthening FOI, January 11, 2023 Issue).

VI. Bringing Government Closer to People: Bringing government closer to people is one of thrusts of public service delivery. This was stressed by P7 who has been in government for 16 years and is currently advocating for financial inclusion of marginalized youth sector.

IV. The Participants’ Contributions to Public Service Delivery

What are the former journalists’ contributions to public service delivery, particularly in the fulfillment of their agencies’ mandate?

Table 4

Notion on the Capacity of Former Journalists to Contribute Skills and Expertise to Public Service Delivery

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
1	Of course. Yung nakikita ko, in the 25-26 years that I have been in government service, yung napaka-importanteng aspeto yung public information eh, di ba? Some would call it propaganda, but hindi. It's just providing people with the right kind of information they need to make the right kind of	Of course. From what I've seen in the 25-26 years that I have been in government service, one of the most important aspects is public information, right? Some might call it propaganda, but it's not. It's about providing people with the right kind of information they need to

	decisions, to make the right kind of impressions.	make informed decisions and form accurate impressions.
2	Definitely. I think there are a number of former media in [Agency X].	
3	Honestly, nung una, akala ko wala. Pero yung sa pagsasama namin ni Cong X, na meron din pala kasi. Like for example, tayo, alam natin yung mga red tape sa gobyerno. So, kumbaga may background tayo as a media practitioner. Alam natin kung ano yung mali. Nakikita natin kung ano yung nagpapabagal sa takbo ng gobyerno. So, nakakacontribute din talaga.	Honestly, at first, I thought there was none. But in working with Cong X, I realized there actually is. For example, we know about the red tape in government. Having a background as a media practitioner, we understand what's wrong. We can see what slows down the government's processes. So, it really does contribute.
4	Definitely, ang sagot dyan, siyempre, yes. Kaya nga tayo kinuha ng ng senador o ng government institutions na to because of your skills, di ba? Kasi very, ano tayo, very flexible tayo, nasanay tayo nagko-cover.	Definitely, the answer is yes. That's why we were hired by the senator or by government institutions—because of our skills, right? We're very flexible; we're used to covering various situations.
5	Yes. Yes. Very much. Ang laking bagay if you're a former journalist. Not necessarily from, regardless kung anong medium, be it radio, I mean, be it broadcast or print, ang laking bagay because we understand kung ano yung kailangan... So, ayun, yun ang advantage natin eh. We can spot already kung ano	Yes, definitely. It's a huge advantage to be a former journalist. It doesn't matter what medium you came from—whether radio, broadcast, or print. The important thing is that we understand what's needed. We can already spot what stories will

	yung story na kakagatin and yung talagang newsworthy.	catch attention and what's truly newsworthy.
6	Definitely. As a former journalist, I was always given the task of writing, writing of policy briefs, technical notes.	
7	Oo, kasi, yun nga, parang nakaka-contribute dahil nga may media interface pa rin naman. Lahat ng government agency may media interface. Pero, ano naman eh, kung iisipin mo, super, super madaling intindihin kung yung mga media practitioner, mag-wo-work sa Public Information Office ng mga government agency	Yes, because, you know, it really contributes because there is still media interface. Every government agency has a media interface. But, if you think about it, it's super easy to understand if media practitioners work in the Public Information Office of government agencies.
8	Yes, I think skills and expertise of former journalists are very, very vital in the delivery of public service, just because it ensures that nadadala talaga sa tao yung kailangang ibigay.	Yes, I believe the skills and expertise of former journalists are crucial in the delivery of public service. They ensure that essential information reaches the public effectively.
9	Ang masasabi ko na contribution ko sa... yung skills...So as a journalist, nandoon yung being transparent. Andun din yung, walang biases.	What I can say about my contribution is my skills. So as a journalist, I put premium on transparency and impartiality, no biases.
10	I would agree na (that) former journalists can contribute. They have a lot to contribute in terms of skills and expertise sa public service...The skills in the work ethics that we gain in	

	working for a private media outfit. They help.	
11	I think yes. It's high time that you know, we journalists or the people coming from the media will also consider government office as a, you know, as an opportunity for them to grow as well. Hindi lang naman yung ahensya na yun ang makikinabang sa 'yo. Ikaw rin naman makikinabang sa kanya (It's not just the agency that will benefit from your skills; you will also benefit).	
12	I think nakaka-contribute naman po yung former media practitioners sa public service delivery. So, since they excel in clear and concise effective communication, which I think is crucial in formulating policies, doing public information campaigns. And mas na-uunderstand po nila yung public concerns. Kasi nandoon na sila sa on the ground eh. Na, nakikita nila harapan kung ano nangyayari sa on the ground. So they can bridge the gap po between the government and yung community.	I believe that former media practitioners can contribute significantly to public service delivery. So, since they excel in clear and concise effective communication, which I think is crucial in formulating policies, doing public information campaigns. They also have a better understanding of public concerns because they've been on the ground, witnessing first-hand what's happening. This experience allows them to effectively bridge the gap between the government and the community.
13	Yes po. Yun nga po. Like I said po, with my training as a journalist, syempre, media po as fourth estate, ganun po yung view natin. I	Yes, exactly. As I mentioned, with my training as a journalist, media as the fourth estate. I personally tend

	<p>personally tend to be critical po of myself and my work being a public servant. Kasi, ayaw ko ng mediocre. Deserve ba ng taong 'to yung ginagawa ko?</p>	<p>to be critical of myself and my work being a public servant. I despise mediocrity. I strive to ensure that my work is not mediocre, and constantly question, does the public deserve what I am doing?</p>
14	<p>Oo naman. Again, babalik tayo dun sa point na, the efficiency of delivering information to public. Once you know what the public wants, di ba? Once you know na, kung ano yung papatok, ma-tatailor fit mo yung main message mo sa public, like for example, agenda setting.</p>	<p>Absolutely. We reiterate the importance of having efficiency in delivering information to the public. Once you understand what the public wants and what will resonate with them, you can tailor your main message to fit their needs. Like for example, agenda setting.</p>
15	<p>Yes na yes (Absolutely). 100 percent. I think, I think journalists and yung skills nila (their skills), definitely can be an asset to any government agency.</p> <p>Kasi things na (Things), like writing, no one does it better than journalists. And writing clearly, communicating clearly and effectively, talagang (really) you can rely on former media practitioners who are now working in government service to do that really well.</p>	

Table 4 shows that all the participants agreed that former media practitioners have something to contribute to public service delivery, particularly in the area of public information services. The participants' communication skills, grit, hard work and extensive experiences in the field and trainings make them assets to the government's continued

quest to ensure the efficient, transparent, prompt, and accountable delivery of public service. Herman et.al (2023) said the functions and roles of journalists in supporting communication between the government and the public are important in daily life. Citing Khatimah, they observed that in the sphere of public policy, journalists have been considered “as a part of the Pentahelix elements that cannot be separated and influence each other in a decision or policy-making.”

The researcher believes that with the presence of former media practitioners in some government agencies, bringing the government closer to people by reinforcing the principles of transparency and accountability through the delivery of credible, prompt and accurate public information services is not far-fetched. Press freedom is intended to build a society where citizens are constantly educated, aiding them to have the right judgment to pick good leaders and exercise their democratic rights without fear (Report on State of Media Freedom in the Philippines 2024 presented during the “1st Philippine Media Safety Summit: Surviving Pandemics and Other Provocations by Challenging Current Paradigms,” CMFR, 2 May 2024).

Table 4.1

Participants’ Actual Contributions to Public Service Delivery

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. PUBLIC INFORMATION/ COMMUNICATIONS/MEDIA RELATIONS		
1	You have to really mount an effective public diplomacy campaign to make them understand what we do. So, yeah, so I use Facebook a lot. I personally engage people. I encourage them to add me and message me directly, which is what I've actually been doing since the social media came about. Yun nga, yung ako talaga sasagot, sasagutin kapag nag-message (I personally respond to them if they have queries). Kasi	

	iba yung (because) personal engagement [is different].	
2	When I'm tasked to do the messaging or to do the press release, which I still do by the way, right now, it's something I can do with my eyes closed, but I always make sure that it's nuanced and at the same time, you're communicating policy...Basically, that's it, being able to deliver fast and communicating policies well.	
3	Gusto natin yung transparent tayo sa, yung gobyerno sa atin. So, kaya kami, open kami sa media noon... We make it a point na open kami lagi sa media, na pag may kailangan silang tanong, sinasagot agad naming, negative or positive yan, sasagutin namin yan.	We want our government to be transparent. So, we were open to the media back then. We made it a point to make ourselves, our agency always be accessible to the media, responding to their questions promptly, whether the inquiries were positive or negative.
4	Tingin ko yung mapanatili and make sure na accurate yung information na binibigay namin sa public. And I think that's very important. And then, dapat totoo lang yung sinusulat mo. And di siya sugar-coated. So, I think yun ang basic responsibility namin eh.	I think it's crucial to maintain and ensure the accuracy of the information we provide to the public. It's very important that what we write is truthful and not sugar-coated. I believe that's our basic responsibility.
5	I have been espousing this sa mga PIO Chiefs na we have to hold press conferences. Pero ideally kasi, to be on the news,	I've been advocating to PIO Chiefs that we need to hold press conferences. Ideally, to get news coverage, you

	kailangan exposure. And ano exposure na ito? Pag-conduct ng press con. Kasi ang press releases, while it can help, limited yung nareach.	need exposure. And what kind of exposure? By conducting press conferences. Press releases, while helpful, have limited reach.
9	Mga requests {sa social media}, so kami rin nagfacilitate non. So dapat talaga narereach out talaga, nakakarating sa public, and even public information. Like kanina (July 23 during Typhoon Carina), walang number coding or sinususpend nila yung number coding, anong oras na, hapon na. So nandun na on point na, nagpost kami sa social media. Kailangan namin gumawa ng postings. And then we post it. We disseminate it to everyone, the media, the public.	All requests [on social media], we facilitate the, So we should really reach out to the public, and the public information reaches the public. Like this afternoon (July 23 during Typhoon Carina), the number coding has been suspended. So that's on point, we posted it on social media. We need to make posting and then we post it. We disseminate it to everyone, the media, the public.
10	Medyo may idea na rin ako na what the media will pursue or what they need, the information na kailangan nila. So I could kumbaga, "guide", or at least give the principal an idea of what the media want. So, kapag tinanong siya or hiningan siya ng statement, may idea siya kung what to answer or what points i-stress niya.	I have a good understanding of what the media will pursue and the information they need. This allows me to "guide" or at least provide the principal with an idea of what the media wants. So, when asked for a statement or response, the principal has already an idea what to answer or the key points that must be emphasized.
11	Pwede ko sabihin na (I can say that my) contribution is that I was able to bring 46 million ROI (return on investment) last year sa	

	media relations naming (in our media relations effort).	
12	So yung own contribution naman po, for me, I think, nakatulong din yung yung networks since parang may connections ka na. Being a reporter kasi marami ka ng networks sa pag-interviews. So, nakaka-help yun sa pagkailangan mo ng data. So, you know na who to contact, meron ka ng contact person. And then, so nakakatulong din siya sa work, especially if you need information or data na wala yung agency.	As for my own contribution, I think my networks have been quite helpful since you have already established connections. As a former reporter, you had established networks because you interviewed a lot. This helps when looking for data. I already know who to contact since you have links with them. This is particularly beneficial, especially if you need information or there is no readily available data in the agency.
13	We produce content po na, thinking how things may be viewed from the other side of the fence na as how media would write it, how the public would take it po on social media. Hindi lang po kami nag-iinform. Parang we consider also the timing, message, value po ng content, before putting it out.	We produce content while considering how things might be viewed from the other side of the fence, such as how the media would write about it and how the public might perceive it on social media. We don't just inform; we also consider the timing, message, and value of the content before putting it out.
14	Other than sending PR, other than releasing newsletters, I was able to help na mag gumawa ng mga media campaign. Kasi hindi lang naman basta release ka ng release, kailangang isipin mo din	Other than sending press releases and newsletters, I was able to contribute by helping to create media campaigns. It's not just about releasing information; you also

	<p>yung timing, yung ano, gestation period, yung mga ganyang bagay. So yan yung knowledge ko na na-impart sa tao sa office.</p> <p>And yung pangalawa, yung kahalagahan din ng media monitoring. I've been telling them na we should get a media monitoring tool na, makikita natin yung mabibase, maa-angle natin. Para data analytics, it's more of the scientific approach of, are we able to hit our targets na parang yung gano baka effective yung PR natin.</p>	<p>need to consider timing, the gestation period, and other factors. This is the knowledge I've shared with the team in the office.</p> <p>Additionally, I've emphasized the importance of media monitoring. I've been telling them; we should get a media monitoring tool so we can track our performance. Data analytics is more of the scientific approach. This helps us evaluate whether we're meeting our targets and how effective our PR efforts are.</p>
15	<p>Because yung mga ginagawa kong deliverables ay for public consumption, andun po yung pagiging detalyado, andun yung pagiging truthful, i-ensure po natin na tama yung nilalagay nating detalye.</p> <p>And andun nga din po yung grit or yung kagustuhan to make sure na okay po yung lumalabas na material sa public. And that it also has an information po na magagamit or beneficial sa public.</p>	<p>Since the deliverables I produce are for public consumption, attention to detail and truthfulness are crucial. We need to ensure that the information we provide is accurate and well-detailed. There's also the grit and determination to make sure that the materials released to the public are of high quality and that they contain useful and beneficial information to the public.</p>
II. PROGRAM DELIVERY/ PUBLIC CONCERNS AND RESPONSE		
3	<p>Nung umupo kami ni Cong. X, we make it a point binawasan namin yung lahat ng mga requirements para</p>	<p>When Cong. X and I took office, we made it a point to reduce all the requirements to speed</p>

	<p>mas mapabilis and sabi namin, lalo na si Cong X, sabi niya na ang gusto ng tao is yung pagkapunta mo makukuha mo yung hinihingi mo. So, we make it a point at that time na dapat pagdating ng umaga ng beneficiaries, kailangan makukuha nila yung kailangan nila within the day. So, nagawa namin yun at that time.</p>	<p>up the process. We said, especially Cong. X, he said that what people need is they get immediate assistance. that when you go you can get what you ask for. So, we make it a point at that time that when the beneficiaries arrive in the morning, they must get what they need within the day. So, we did that at that time.</p>
7	<p>Actually, yung Office namin instrumental din sa pag-form ng (Paleng QR-Ph) dahil in partnership with DILG and syempre yung LGU. So parang nag-work kami together para mag-issue ng guidelines, yung Joint Memorandum Circular, and joining yung LGUs all over the country to implement the Paleng-QR Ph program.</p> <p>Pero yung team namin, yung particular sector na involved kami is yung youth. Kasi yung youth marginalized sector</p>	<p>Actually, our Office was instrumental in forming the Paleng QR-Ph initiative. We collaborated with the DILG and local government units. We worked together to issue guidelines through the Joint Memorandum Circular and engaged local government units across the country to implement the Paleng QR-Ph program. Specifically, our team focused on the youth sector, recognizing that it is a marginalized group.</p>
9	<p>No backlogs...At least sa Office natin, [on] time on target tayo. Kasi may time din yan eh, we respond to the concerns, the complaints we receive. So yung contribution, Complete work task. At saka, another pa na contribution is, dahil nga din, may mga bago na rin kaming mga writers sa office. Contributions ko is to</p>	<p>No backlogs. At least in our Office, we are on time, on target. Because our response is time-bound, we respond to the concerns, the complaints we've received. So, the contribution, Complete work task. Additionally, another contribution is because we have new</p>

	teach them how we work, how we work, how I work nun as a journalist. And, i-impart din sa kanila yung mga learnings na yun para we are on the same page, in sync, lahat ng mga ginagawa namin.	writers in the Office, I teach them how we currently work, how I worked as a journalist. I impart to them all these learnings to ensure that we are all aligned and in sync with our work.
III. POLICY DEVELOPMENT/PROJECT APPROVAL		
6	So, because of my background, I was pushed to this area of policy dev, policy development. So, I think I was able to contribute to that output of the government agency I'm in.	
8	For me, halimbawa, since I sit in the management, yung purview ng tao over the projects or the proposals that go over us, yun yung contribution ko. We ensure that the proposals that we approve are truly beneficial to the people. We ensure na there are safeguards, in terms of accountability and transparency as well for when, when we, when, when we approve proposals.	For me, since I sit in management, my contribution involves overseeing the projects or proposals that come across our desk. We ensure that the proposals we approve are genuinely beneficial to the public. We also implement safeguards to ensure accountability and transparency in the approval process.

Table 4.1 shows how the former journalist-participants translated their roles into concrete actions, providing the complete picture of their actual contributions to government's public service delivery. They are very much involved and engaged in the delivery of public information services.

This study grouped the participants' actual contributions into three facets: (1) Public Information/Communications/Media Relations, (2) Program Delivery/Public Concerns and Response; and (3) Policy Development/Project Approval.

I. Public Information/Communications/Media Relations: Twelve (12) participants who are mostly working in the Executive, Legislative and Judicial branches of government and

had a media experience of one (1) to 20 years are into public information, communications and media relations. P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, and P15 belong to the first group of government communicators.

II. Program Delivery/Public Concerns and Response: Three (3) participants - P3, P7, and P9 are very much involved in the implementation of programs by their respective agencies.

III. Policy Development/Project Approval: Two (2) participants, namely P6 and P8 are into project proposal approval and policy development in fulfilment of their roles.

As former members of the “fourth estate,” the participants remain committed to carry over and keep the press’ watchdog tradition – always being on a lookout to ensure the transparent and accountable delivery of public service. Journalism promotes a healthy civic space by providing trusted and fact-based information which is essential to people’s participation in a free and open society (Highlights of the World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022, “Journalism is a Public Good”, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization 2021). Herman et.al (2023) cited the crucial roles of journalists to bridge the communication between the government and the public. They stressed that the fourth estate should always be on board in public decision or policy-making.

V. The Participants’ Suggestions to Strengthen Partnership to Curb Corruption, and Promote Transparency and Accountability in the Bureaucracy

How can former journalists effectively engage with the government as partners in disseminating its programs and projects to curb corruption, and promote transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy?

Table 5

Participants’ Suggestions on How to Strengthen Partnership with the Government as Anti-Corruption and Pro-Transparency and Accountability Mechanism in Public Service Delivery

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
I. OPEN ACCESS/INFORMATION DELIVERY		
3	Sa akin talaga kasi, parang napaka importante ng transparency eh. Kasi, kung transparent ka, kasunod na	For me, transparency is really important. Because if you are transparent, it naturally

	<p>doon yung ma-eradicate mo yung corruption eh, di ba? And kung open ka sa lahat, nakikita ng taong bayan yung ginagawa mo. sa gobyerno.</p>	<p>follows that you can reduce corruption, right? And if you're open about everything, the public can see what you're doing.</p>
4	<p>So, during budget season, di ba, so gumagawa rin kami ng mga press releases. So, bawat ahensya ng gobyerno, tinatalakay sa [Legislative] yung budget. So, we make sure na yung binibigay naming details, tama. Paglabas sa [Legislative] website, pagblast namin yan sa media entities, tama. So, yung transparency dun, tingin ko, nasa-serve namin. Plus yung accountability na dapat tama yung figures and everything. All information, the data, the figures na nilalabas namin, dapat tama.</p>	<p>So, during budget season, we also produce press releases. Each government agency discusses its budget in the [Legislative]. We make sure that the details we provide are accurate. When we publish information on the [Legislative] website and send it out to media entities, it has to be correct. In terms of transparency, I think we serve it well. Plus, the accountability aspect means that the figures and all the information we release must be accurate.</p>
7	<p>Gumawa ng better communication material, siguro parang seryosohin...So, siguro yun, more, better materials, better communication products para mapansin ng media and ma-report na may ginagawang maayos yung [Independent Public Financial Institution X]. Transparency na rin sa ginagawa namin.</p>	<p>Create better communication materials...So, I think it's about producing better materials and communication products to get media attention and report the good work being done by the [Independent Public Financial Institution X]. It also involves ensuring transparency in what we do.</p>
9	<p>Walang dapat itago... So, dapat talaga transparent</p>	<p>There's nothing to hide... So, a truly</p>

	working relationship. Yes, transparent. And then, you follow the procedure. No shortcuts. You follow the system.	transparent working relationship is necessary. Yes, transparent. And then, you follow the procedure. No shortcuts. You follow the system.
14	Ang lagi ko lang kasing in-advise sa kanila is hindi mo kailangan magtago... it's more of, wala kang tinatago. Wala kang tinatago. So, it's a matter of how frequent you're informing the public of what's happening, how prompt you are in terms of answering issues.	What I always advise them is that you don't need to hide anything... It's more about not hiding anything. So, it's a matter of how frequent you're informing the public of what's happening, how prompt you are in terms of answering issues.
II. VALUES		
1	Alam mo dapat ano yung mission mo... We get sent out to serve our people, to serve our country. Lalo yung focus mo, huwag ka mawala dun. I'm lucky I belong to an agency of government that is not known for corruption. Maraming safety nets that were put in place to make sure that walang magiging corrupt sa amin.	You need to know what your mission is... We get sent out to serve our people, to serve our country. Stay focused on that. There are many safety nets in place to ensure that no one engages in corruption.
5	First and foremost, dapat you have integrity na muna. When you join the government, mag-join ka for the proper reasons. The only way para makinig sa'yo, yung mga yung mga officials sa government is for you to build that reputation.	First and foremost, you should have integrity. When you join the government, you should do so for the right reasons. The only way to get government officials to listen to you is by building that reputation.

8	<p>If they want to engage government, they would have to, well, participate in the government process. Madaling magsalita if you're outside. Pero once you're in the system and you need to effect change, yun yung challenge. (It's easy to speak from the outside, but once you're inside the system and need to effect change, that's the real challenge). Maraming considerations along the way and you will have to conquer those. Another is that you go back to your why. Why do you want this? And what really drives you? Kasi kung hindi mo i-ga-ground yung sarili mo (If you don't ground yourself), you'll be lost in the system. And sooner or later, you'll just be part of the problem that you hope to solve when you get into government.</p>	
10	<p>One way would be, you have to establish trust with current media practitioners, and with government officials concerned. Siguro find a way to... I don't know if middle ground is the right term, but we have to find a way to relay yung (the) key information sa (to the) media. Yung focus niya (The focus) is promoting accountability, pero (while) avoiding also yung sensationalism na baka matabunan di ba, yung issue dahil may gustong i-promote</p>	

	na something else (that might overshadow the issue because of other agenda).	
III. TRANSPARENCY MECHANISMS/INITIATIVES		
2	That's tough. Because, first of all, those mechanisms have to be in place within government agencies to promote transparency, accountability, anti-corruption. If none, then media will have to be really assertive and will have to take the initiative to demand for that across all government agencies.	
11	It's high time that they see the government as an opportunity for them to work. Hindi naman kailangan na yung trabaho nila dito ay regular positions (It's not necessary that their work here should be in regular positions). I think that the government should also be open in getting them as a consultant, especially for people into communication.	
12	I think they can advocate and help establish transparency initiatives, such as open data platforms and they can also help establish public reporting systems that allow citizens to access information about government operations and about government spending them. I think yun yung nakikita kong role for them	

	(that's the role I see for them).	
15	Proposing activities po na can invite yung transparency and accountability sa mga government employees, sa mga public service, public servants. Pero definitely, kailangan mo po talagang i-formalize yung mga ganong proposals. Like you have to talk to your supervisors maybe. You might have to draft that proposal yourself para maakyat siya sa management for review and their consideration.	Proposing activities that can promote transparency and accountability among government employees and public servants. But definitely, you really need to formalize such proposals. For example, you have to talk to your supervisors and perhaps draft the proposal yourself to submit it for management review and consideration.
IV. TRAINING/IMMERSION		
6	In terms of engagement, I think media practitioners can also look into, they really have to study the agencies they are assigned to cover. Kasi pag may nakatingin sa kanila (Because if you are asserting your watchdog role), we can help them improve, also their processes, they can help them be more accountable as to their mandate, as to their goals and vision.	
13	I think media training po is important. Me, as part of private media before, na we can educate government offices po na how to effectively communicate things or programs, per se, so that people would know and actually engage and	I think media training is important. As part of private media before, we can educate government offices on how to effectively communicate things or programs, per se, so that people are informed, engaged, and

	actually participate sa ginagawa ng government.	involved in what the government is doing.
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Table 5 encompasses participants’ diverse suggestions as to how they can effectively engage with the government as partners to curb corruption, and promote transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy.

The participants’ suggestions were clustered into four themes: (1) Transparency Mechanisms/Initiatives, (2) Values, (3) Open Access/Information Delivery; and (4) Training and Immersion.

I. Open Access/Information Delivery: The participants stated that all-out transparency in the government is a fight against corruption. P3, P9, and P14 stressed the importance of providing full information access to public, and that the government processes and procedures are strictly followed. As government communicators, the participants (P4 and P7) mentioned that there should be a provision of quality communication materials and products, and that accurate and reliable data and information should be made available to the public in a prompt manner. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2021) said the delivery of trusted and fact-based information is significant to people’s participation in a free and open society (Highlights of the World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022, “Journalism is a Public Good”).

II. Values: The participants commonly identified sense of values in terms of untainted integrity, and credible reputation; and commitment to public trust as major key ingredients for their strengthened partnership with the government to lessen corruption, and promote transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy. P1, P5, P8, and P10, who all had extensive media and government experiences, discussed that given the challenges hounding the public sector, it is stressed that to make a difference, one must have the following: integrity and credible reputation, sense of mission, and commitment to serve the public to positively impact the spectrum of governance, particularly in the delivery of public services. Serving the people with integrity, utmost responsibility, and efficiency is non-negotiable. During the 50th anniversary of the Kapisanan ng mga Brodkaster ng Pilipinas (KBP), President Marcos Jr. urged the broadcast organization “take the lead and foster public discussions, truth, and credibility” (Locus, 2023).

III. Transparency Mechanisms/Initiatives: The participants cited the need to put in place pro-transparency and accountability and anti-corruption mechanisms in all government agencies. P2, P11, P12, and P15 who were from print and broadcast media sectors mentioned that necessary initiatives must be implemented to promote transparency and accountability in the government. P12, a female print journalist, specifically suggested that open data platforms and establishment of public reporting systems that allow citizens to access information about the government operations and spending be considered. Meanwhile, P11 manifested that it is about high time for government to considering tapping the expertise of media practitioners as consultants.

IV. Training/Immersion: The participants stressed the need to conduct trainings and immersion stint to move forward the advocacy of promoting transparency and accountability in the government service. P6 specifically stated that the watchdog tradition should be asserted to help government agencies become more accountable as to their mandate, goals and visions. P13, on the other hand, stressed that government offices should be trained or educated on how to effectively communicate public programs so that that people are informed, engaged, and involved in what the government is doing.

VI. The Participants’ Policy Recommendations for the Promotion of Transparent and Accountable Public Service Delivery

What policy can be developed to enhance and strengthen the involvement of former media practitioners in promoting transparency and accountability in public service delivery?

Table 6

Participants’ Policy Recommendations for Transparent and Accountable Public Service Delivery

Participant Number	Verbatim	English Translation
ACCELERATING COMMUNICATIONS’ LEVEL IN GOVERNMENT AGENCIES		
3	We have to accelerate yung level of communications ng mga government agencies. And yung transparency na rin siguro, na yun yung hinahanap din ng media. And not even media, yung publiko mismo, di ba?	We need to accelerate the level of communications within government agencies. And also, improve transparency, which is something that both the media and the public are looking for.
5	I’ve been suggesting before na maging policy na to make each press conferences, regular. I mean, regular, that this be done on a regular basis. Kasi it’s the only way para maka reach out sa tao, maka reach out sa masa.	I’ve been suggesting before that it should become policy to make press conferences regular. I mean, they should be done on a regular basis. It’s the only way to reach out to people, to the masses.

8	<p>Another is the use of technology. One thing that we did is to have the things that we have in, ano, available to the public, para hindi mo na siya ire-request through FOI, di ba? Nandun na siya. And tayo as comms practitioners, look out natin yun na madali siyang mahanap. Kasi tayo yung may ganong lente. Alam natin paano mag-behave yung tao in terms of doing searches, in terms of accessing government services. So, yun, contribution natin yun. We should do that. Pero yun nga, we should not be afraid of technology and instead use it to our advantage.</p>	<p>Another aspect is the use of technology. One thing we did was to make available to the public the information that was previously requested through FOI. It's now easily accessible. As communications practitioners, we need to ensure that this information is easy to find. We understand how people search for and access government services, so this is our contribution. We should embrace technology and use it to our advantage.</p>
9	<p>So, I think one policy which I can suggest is the process, like for example, the documentation. Dapat documented every step of the way. So for that documentation, there should be a process. The scheme should be well-documented. Kung pwede, talagang approved by the management na dapat na andun yun na evidence-based talaga lahat ng mga gagawin. Lahat ng initiatives [well-documented], from visibility up to budgeting pa nga sana eh.</p>	<p>So, I think one policy I can suggest is related to the process, such as documentation. Every step of the way should be documented. There should be a clear process for this documentation. The scheme should be well-documented, and if possible, it should be approved by management so that there is evidence-based documentation for all actions taken. All initiatives should be well-documented, from visibility to budgeting, ideally</p>

15	[Agency X] is a lot of numbers, a lot of data. It's truly difficult to communicate numbers to people. Kung specific po sa agency (If specific for agency), parang (but) there's definitely potential in tapping TikTok. Merong official account si [Agency X] sa TikTok pero it's not yet maximized kasi parang in-explore pa siya sa ngayon. (Agency X has an official TikTok account, but it's not fully maximized yet, as it's still being explored.)	
STRENGTHENING OF FOI		
3	Sa akin talaga, sobrang push sa akin yung yung FOI na yan, yung Freedom of Information, kasi sobrang malaking tulong yan kasi pinaglalaman nga natin yung transparency eh, di ba? So, sa akin talaga, sobrang pabor ako dyan sa FOI na yan.	For me, the Freedom of Information (FOI) is something I strongly support because it's a huge help in advocating for transparency. I am very much in favor of the FOI.
4	Tingin ko kailangan yun (FOI) eh. Kailangan natin ng batas. To strengthen yung public information.	I think we need that (FOI). We need a law to strengthen public information.
7	Parang makakatulong din naman [ang strengthening ng FOI]. Kasi syempre yung mga tao, para empowered sila na magtanong, sila lang mismo.	This could also help (FOI strengthening) because the people are empowered to ask.
8	Kung totoong open data ka, i-open mo talaga...The way forward pag sa FOI is to	If you are truly for open data, have everything opened for access. The

	<p>have it public. Kasi may ang obvious naman na hindi mo talaga pwedeng ilagay sa publiko ay halimbawa, personal information...Pero kung halimbawa proyekto yan na pinopondohan naman ng mga tao, if it is not covered by intellectual property, then why hide it?</p>	<p>way forward with FOI is to have it public. Because obviously, you can't make public personal information. But, for example, if the project is funded by public funds, if it is not covered by intellectual property, then why hide it?</p>
14	<p>Ako talaga Freedom of information. So, pag institutionalize yan, mas empowered yung kumukuha ng information. Not only the media, but the public. So, it will really promote transparency. Kasi easy access yun eh. And for me, kung ikaw nga, politiko naman, kung wala ka naman tinatago, pabor din sa'yo yun.</p>	<p>For me, it's definitely the Freedom of Information (FOI). If it is institutionalized, it will empower not only the media but also the public in obtaining information. This will really promote transparency because it provides easy access. And for politicians, if you have nothing to hide, it would also be beneficial for you.</p>
III. MEDIA HIRING		
5	<p>Ang naisip ko din, ang I've noticed kasi, I'm not familiar with the other institutions, pero siguro, iba kasi yung ano ng Civil Service. Sa government ka kasi, kahit na information officer ka, parang ang strict ng mga qualifications. If you've noticed, pag, I don't know kung may na-interview ka na before, na who said na, pagdating sa civil service kasi, para ma-promote ka, kailangan may MA ka, [may trainings}, may mga fellowship ganyan. Kasi parang, gusto kong maging policy na, alam mo yun,</p>	<p>What I've noticed is that, although I'm not familiar with other institutions, the Civil Service has strict qualifications. Even if you're an information officer, it's quite stringent. If you've interviewed someone before, you might have heard that to get promoted in civil service, you need to have an MA, specific trainings, fellowships, and so on. I think there should be a policy that considers experience, especially for former journalists, not just academic</p>

	hindi lang yun dapat basis, lalo na pag former journalist ka, they have to take into account yung experience ng applicant. That should be considered.	qualifications. Experience should be taken into account for applicants who are former journalists.
7	Siguro, non-discrimination sa hiring ng mga former media practitioners.	Perhaps, there should be non-discrimination in hiring former media practitioners.
8	Kasi ever since I joined government, I've seen so many promising talents na umaalis because the structure is not there for them to stay. Walang plantilla positions. Tapos syempre yung system, minsan may talent na yung former media practitioner, pero minsan ang nakukuha pa rin yung mga bata-bata ng mga kung sino-sino.	Since I joined the government, I've seen so many promising talents leave because the structure isn't in place for them to stay. There are no plantilla positions. Sometimes, even though a former media practitioner has the talent, the positions often go to candidates who have connections.
11	Dapat in-offer nung mga seasoned journalists yung kanilang mismong expertise to the government...There should be a direct collaboration, that kami ang hahawak ng comms nyo. Kami ang tutulong sa inyo. There should be a policy to that.	The seasoned journalists should offer their expertise to the government. There should be direct collaboration [between the government and media organizations] that we will handle your communications, we will help you. There should be policy to that.
IV. SKILLS UPGRADING		
3	Siguro, sa 'kin, i-enhance natin yung communication skills, i-enhance natin yung policy pagdating sa, yung pagturing sa media. Kasi yun, di ba, yung nabanggit ko kanina na palaging ang	For me, we should enhance communication skills and improve policy regarding interactions with the media. Because, as I mentioned earlier, there's often a perception

	tingin lagi ng mga government officials, ng mga public officials sa media is kaaway kasi. Nakita talaga namin na malaking bagay yung communications,i- enhance mo yung communication skills, yung pakitungo mo sa publiko para may parating mo yung ginagawa mo.	among government and public officials that the media is an enemy. We've seen how important communication is; you improve your communication skills and how you deal with the public iso that you convey what you're doing.
5	Kailangan ng constant learning, hangga't maaari magkaroon ng, what you call this, yung consistent upgrade pagdating sa skills na. If pwede namang i-allow ng institution to provide seminars, for us, para sa mga workers. Kasi ano eh, tawag dito, kailangan ng constant upgrading ng skills eh, lalo na ngayon kasi sobrang fast-paced ang mundo, with the advent ng socmed.	Constant learning is essential. Institutions should allow for continuous skill upgrades. It would be beneficial if institutions could provide seminars for workers. Constant upgrading of skills is necessary, especially now with the fast-paced world and the advent of social media.
13	Media training, trainings on, not necessarily what the media wants, how the media wants to be treated. Pero like, trainings with the media on how to communicate effectively, [on how to effectively report government programs], and also skills enhancement so we know how to be flexible, adapt, innovate.	
V. GATHERING OF GOVERNMENT COMMUNICATORS		
3	[Gathering of government communicators to share best practices) sa lahat ng	[Gathering of government communicators to share best practices] in all

	government agency, I think, that's very good step na dapat matuloy and huwag mawala. Kasi importante yun eh. Kasi, alam mo yung, di ba minsan nakikita mo naman sa gobyerno, yung hindi-synchronize yung mga communications nila.	government agencies, I think that's a very good step that should continue and not be discontinued. It's important because, sometimes, you see that government communications are not synchronized.
10	Siguro, one suggestion that I could make is regular meetings between former media practitioners and siguro the concerned government officials, lalo na yung mga PIOs. So, mashe-share nila yung experiences nila. And in the process, matututo yung mga PIOs na, ito yung best practices at yung mga mga bawal or unethical sa industriya, para they can they can adopt the good and then they can also avoid the bad.	One suggestion I could make is to have regular meetings between former media practitioners and the concerned government officials, especially the PIOs This would allow them to share their experiences. In the process, the PIOs can learn about best practices and what to avoid or what is considered unethical in the industry. This way, they can adopt the good practices and avoid the bad ones.
12	And we can also create forums where former media practitioners can also mentor and collaborate with current journalists.	
VI. NATIONAL POLICY FOR ALL		
1	It should be a national policy na address sa lahat...What we need are Filipinos na nag-iisip para sa mas nakararami, hindi para sa sarili. If you're in government, how could you help ensure transparency? Be a watchdog.	It should be a national policy that addresses everyone. What we need are Filipinos who think about the greater good, not just for themselves. If you're in government, how could you help

		ensure transparency? Be a watchdog.
2	So the policy should be for everyone. The policy shouldn't be focused on you being a former media practitioner, but it should be for the entire bureaucracy. It's gonna be a tough, job to do. There are policies already in place, but the problem is really the implementation.	
VII. OTHER RECOMMENDATIONS		
A. SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTABILITY		
4	I think that's very important, proposed measure na sana maipasa natin about social media accountability, how to really fight information dissemination, fake news, misinformation, and disinformation.	I think it's very important to pass a proposed measure about social media accountability, focusing on how to effectively combat the dissemination of fake news, misinformation, and disinformation.
B. MEDIA PARTICIPATION IN GOVERNMENT CONSULTATIONS		
6	A. In terms of policy, government kasi has demanded to be consultative. So I think that it should be encouraged, if not mandated, to include the media in consultations, given that the media is one of the stakeholders also in all the things that we do in government.	

C. IMMERSION OF MEDIA IN GOVERNMENT		
6	<p>More of the media side, is to really show...they're really interested in what the government office is doing and how the government office can improve and how the government office can reach to more of its constituents or stakeholders.</p> <p>So, I think yung mas, mas masigasig siguro yung media natin (So I think our media should be more tenacious) in covering issues relating to government agencies.</p>	
D. CREATION OF INDEPENDENT MONITORING BODY		
12	<p>I think the former media professionals, they can help establish independent bodies to monitor and evaluate government transparency and accountability practices. And they can publish their findings and recommendations to foster public trust and to also drive improvements in public service delivery.</p>	
E. GRANTS FOR INVESTIGATIVE JOURNALISM PROJECTS		
12	<p>I think government agencies can encourage investigative journalism. I think government can explore in providing grants or support for investigative journalism projects that focus on government</p>	

	transparency and also public accountability. service	
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Table 6 tackles the participants' varied policy recommendations that could enhance and strengthen the involvement of former media practitioners in promoting transparency and accountability in public service delivery. The proposed policies were clustered into seven major themes: (1) Accelerate Communications' Level in Government Agencies; (2) Strengthening of the Freedom of Information (FOI); (3) Media Hiring in Government; (4) Skills Upgrading; (5) Gathering of Government Communicators; (6) National Policy for All; and (7) Other Recommendations.

The first two proposed policies commonly identified by the participants were: Accelerate Communications' Level in Government Agencies; and the Strengthening of the FOI.

I. Accelerate Communications' Level in Government Agencies: Five participants (P3, P5, P8, P9, and P15) agreed that the level of communications in government agencies must be accelerated. Two participants (P8 and P15) specifically sought the use of digital technology in improving the level of communications in the government agencies. The regular conduct of press conferences and media briefings was then proposed by P5, who has been with the Judiciary for 22 years, as a mechanism to enhance transparency and accountability in the government. As the Center for Media Freedom and Responsibility (2024) prodded the newsrooms to take a second look at their old ways, innovate, and explore new approaches to engage the people again and connect with the new ways they live their lives (CMFR Report on State of Media Freedom in the Philippines 2024 presented during the "1st Philippine Media Safety Summit: Surviving Pandemics and Other Provocations by Challenging Current Paradigms," 2 May 2024), the government agencies should put forward innovative reforms to public information delivery.

II. Strengthening of the FOI: To strengthen the public information delivery and promote the culture of transparency and accountability in the country, FOI must be strengthened. This was the common policy recommendation made by five participants, who were mostly senior journalists (P3, P4, P7, P8, and P14). In its Editorial, the Philippine Daily Inquirer (2023) challenged President Marcos Jr. "to reverse" the reduced adherence to transparency and good governance under the watch of his predecessor by directing the government institutions to "deepen their commitment to freedom of information (FOI) principles." Based on the Philippine Center for Investigative Journalism (PCIJ) 2022 report, the approval of FOI requests only stood at 40 percent, which was only half of its 80-percent approval rate target (PDI, Editorial: Strengthening FOI, January 11, 2023 Issue). The PDI (2023) furthered that the Chief Executive should also be a role model of transparency, accountability, and openness for all other state officials to follow.

III. Media Hiring in Government: Tapping the expertise of media likewise surfaced, with four participants (P5, P7, P8, and P11) raising this proposed policy. P5, P8, and P11 specifically pushed for the regularization of experienced media practitioners who are in the government service by considering their extensive media experience as a major factor of providing plantilla positions for them.

IV. Skills Upgrading: Three (3) participants (P3, P5, and P13) who are mostly senior journalists suggested that there must be continued skills upgrading for government communicators for them to effectively communicate policies, and programs in the public sector. P5 specifically mentioned the need for the enhancement of communications and media relations skills due to fast-paced technology and surging social media users. Herman et.al (2023) said media companies, overwhelmed by the social media development, are remiss of providing comprehensive information regarding government programs, and “are not optimal in conveying public complaints to the government.” With this scenario, the government communicators should step up and ensure that the public information must be promptly and fully delivered to the people.

V. Gathering of Government Communicators: Three (3) participants (P3, P10, and P12) saw the need to create fora where there will be sharing of best practices, and partnership will be forged between the former media practitioners and current journalists. This will help ensure synchronized communications plans of all agencies. As President Marcos Jr. urged the KBP to “take the lead and foster public discussions, truth, and credibility,” (Locus, 2023), the researcher believes that the government communicators should also proactively participate in keeping a well-informed citizenry.

VI. National Policy for All: Two participants (P1 and P2) who both had extensive media and government experience stated that the promotion of transparency and accountability in public service delivery should be the responsibility of all sectors, not just by former journalists who are now working in the government. P1, a veteran news editor and experienced government official, shared that everyone should be a watchdog to really promote transparency and accountability in the delivery of public service. P2 specifically pointed out that the policy should not only focus on being a former media practitioner, but it should be for the entire bureaucracy. Holliday (2021) stressed that “effective democracy requires accurate information that engages communities in civic life.” Everyone must be “willing and able to participate, not just as news consumers, but as distributors and—most important—producers of local information” (Holliday, 2021).

VII. Other Recommendations: P4, 6, and P12 also pushed for media involvement in the government process, such as social media regulation, policymaking, evaluation and monitoring of best practices.

Social Media Accountability: P4, an experienced print journalist who has been with the Legislative for 14 years, stressed the need to fight fake news, misinformation, and disinformation which may hamper transparency and accountability in public service delivery. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2021) said the “disinfodemic” or the “pandemic of false information” resulted in the declining trust in media globally, an opportunity for some political leaders to exploit the deluge of

mis- and disinformation to attack the legitimacy of critical and independent media (World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development: Global Report 2021/2022, “Journalism is a Public Good”).

Media Participation in Government Consultations: P6, a female former print journalist who has been with the government for 14 years, cited the importance of including the media in government consultations. She said a media representative should sit as one of the members of a government panel that is deliberating on a certain policy or guidelines. Herman et.al (2023) stressed that the fourth estate should always be on board in public decision or policy-making, as they significantly bridge the communication between the government and the public.

Immersion of Media in Government: P6 also said that the media should be interested in what the government office is doing so they can give inputs as to how such government agency or institution can improve its processes and the public service delivery in general, as well as to how it can broadly reach or cover its clients or stakeholders. President Marcos Jr. had urged the media “to effectively communicate to the public the government’s efforts and initiatives towards our country’s development” (Presidential Communications Office, 2022).

Creation of Independent Monitoring Body: P12, a female former print journalist who is engaged in policy/program reviews and research, said former media practitioners can help establish independent bodies to monitor and evaluate government transparency and accountability practices, given their experience. She proposed the creation of an independent panel, composed of former media practitioners, that will be tasked with keeping an eye on government agencies’ pro-transparency and accountability efforts. The panel will publish the findings and recommendations to foster public trust and to help improve the delivery of public services.

Grants for Investigative Journalism Projects: P12 likewise sought government grants for investigative journalism projects focused on government transparency and public service accountability. She said the government should explore on providing grants to the news media sector to promote transparency and accountability in the government.

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the essential core of the study’s evidence-based findings, informed conclusions and data-driven recommendations, effectively addressing the research problems raised in this study. Under this section, the researcher provides the synthesized insights or findings that form part of the conclusion. Furthermore, this chapter lays down the best possible recommendations, which include policy formulation and program development. These recommendations are based on the insights or findings culled from the study.

The study is summed and divided into seven segments: (1) Participants' Profile; (2) Political, economic, social, and personal reasons behind the migration of print, broadcast and multimedia journalists to the government service; (3) Roles of former media practitioners in their respective agencies; (4) Perceptions about public service delivery; (5) Contributions to public service delivery; (6) Suggestions to strengthen partnership to curb corruption, and promote transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy, and (7) Policies to be recommended for promotion of transparent and accountable public service delivery.

Based on the data presented in a tabular format, the findings or insights of the study were the following:

1. Profile of the Respondents

As to age. Data reveals that the participants are within the ages of 25 and 58 years old. Majority of them are 36 - 46 years old, and 47 - 57 years old, suggesting that the participants in the study are Millennials and Generation X.

As to gender. Data shows that women's all-out participation in the study is evident with eight female former media practitioners joining the study. However, it also showed that men were equally willing to participate in the study with seven of them participating in the study.

As to years of media experience. Most participants had extensive media experience ranging from 10 years to 20 years. Based on their media service in the private sector, the participants were categorized as follows: A. 5 years and below; B. 6-10 years; and C. 11-20 years in service or more. Based on this category, majority of the participants belong to Category B with a media experience ranging from six to 10 years.

As to media affiliations. Majority of the participants were print media journalists, with nine of them participating in the study. Former journalists from the broadcast companies and multimedia news platforms were also equally represented in this study, with the inclusion of three respondents belonging to each sector.

As to government-employer. Majority of the participants are working in agencies under the Executive branch of government. The second largest number of participants is logged in the Legislative.

As to government-positions. Majority of the participants are holding permanent and supervisory positions in the government.

2. Reasons behind the Migration of Print, Broadcast and Multimedia Journalists to the Government Service

A. Political. A relatively small number of participants mentioned political as a reason why they left their profession to enter the government service. The study cites four

major political reasons: political influence, political denial, media harassment, and biased and anti-workers' workplace policies. Of these, political influence emerges as the first political reason, followed by political denial, media harassment, and biased and anti-workers' workplace policies. The study finds that some former media practitioners entered the government service through political influence or their affiliation with the officials in the government. Given the participants' extensive media experience (ranging from seven to 20 years) and exposure to government dealings and processes, political leaders tapped their expertise to be of service to the government.

The study also bares the deliberate attempts to restrict press freedom and the public's rights of access to information by some political authorities and private companies as evident in the political denial of validated news stories, and media harassment through filing of libel cases. Amid threats of harassment, imprisonment, violence, or death, the press tradition of watchdog remains alive.

The study likewise shows that media repression is being perpetuated by the media owners themselves due to their purported vested interests. The supposed vested "political and economic interests" of the media owners who are from influential families, and conglomerates, caused repression within their organization.

B. Economic. Majority of the participants overwhelmingly responded that economic was the reason why they migrated to the government service, making it as the main reason behind the newsroom-to-government phenomenon.

The financial security in the public sector, financial insecurity in the media sector, and family needs were the key reasons behind their decision to leave their respective media companies.

The higher compensation in the government is identified as the top economic reason, followed by the security of tenure, and provisions of benefits

In terms of financial insecurity in the media sector, majority of the respondents identified the lack of benefits (such as overtime and hazard pay and night differential, retirement package, insurance, enough transportation allowance, and healthcare protection scholarships, and trainings), as their major reason for leaving their media companies. This is followed by low compensation and absence of clear tenure.

The study also shows that the participants' quests to start and raise a family, and find a viable and stable family income also become a major factor why they had to leave their media profession.

C. Social. Social was the second leading reason why participants changed their career path. Most participants cited social as their reason for quitting their jobs. This study shows that the working conditions in the media sector prodded them to work for the government. The irregular working hours, the unclear work delineation that resulted in intense workload, and the slow career progression are commonly identified as factors under the working conditions.

The study also finds that the workload in the media sector was more intense and heavier during the COVID-19 pandemic when media companies implemented work-from-home policies.

Next to working conditions, the participants identified their sense of mission, social influence and time with family as another major social reasons.

The study shows the changing media landscape in the country, particularly the influence of the digital technology and social media, and their impact to the news media sector. The dying print media is mentioned as another major reason why the participants changed their profession, given the declining public support for the print media due to the emergence of social media platforms.

Moreover, corruption in the media sector is likewise found as another major social reason. The participants cited that some of their colleagues succumbed to bribery because of low salaries and lack of benefits in the media sector.

It is also disclosed in this study that the work schedule in the government is more family-friendly than in the media sector.

D. Personal. After economic, personal was the third leading reason why media practitioners had to transfer to government service. The participants mentioned personal/professional growth as their first personal reason, followed by health and a change in environment.

This study found that job burnout was prominent during the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. Roles of Former Media Practitioners in their Respective Agencies

Most participants are involved in the delivery of public information services. Next to public information services, media and public relations becomes the second major role of the participants in their government agencies. Public and cultural diplomacy, program or project management and events management are found to be the third major role of the participants.

It is observed that the mandate of their respective agencies dictates the participants' roles in government service.

The participants working in Executive and Legislative agencies are into substantive policy work and in crisis communication/ management, while participants from Executive agencies are engaged in research and conducting studies.

The participants assumed varied roles in the government. These include administrative work, policy/program/project review, planning, and public concerns and response management.

3. Perceptions About Public Service Delivery

Majority of the participants believed that public servants should exemplify professionalism, competence, ethics, dedication and commitment to public trust when it comes to public service delivery; and that efficient, prompt, and all-out delivery of public service must be prioritized at all costs.

The participants' negative perception about the government changed or their initial view of government service was reinforced when they entered the government service. Their immersion in their respective agencies that are actively involved in public service delivery makes them realize that those in the government have been doing a lot in spirit of genuine service and for love of country.

The study shows that providing accurate, credible and precise information in an efficient, timely and professional manner is a form of public service delivery. The participants believe that a well-informed citizenry is instrumental to democratic governance and sustainable development.

The study also reveals that the continued quest for transparency and accountability in the delivery of public service remains, and that more work still needs to be done to enhance transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy.

4. Notion on the Capacity of Former Journalists to Contribute Skills and Expertise to Public Service Delivery

All the participants cast no doubts on the capacity of former journalists to contribute to public service delivery, particularly in the area of public information services. Their current roles in their respective agencies proved that they have something to contribute to the efficient, transparent, prompt, and accountable delivery of public service.

These former media-turned-government workers can be considered as government assets, considering their excellent communication skills, grit, hard work and extensive experiences in the field and their specialized trainings.

The presence of former media practitioners in some government agencies helps bring the government closer to people by reinforcing the principles of transparency and accountability through the delivery of credible, prompt and accurate public information services.

4.1 Contributions to Public Service Delivery

The former journalist-participants' actual contributions to public service delivery reflected on their commitment to effectively, efficiently, and faithfully carry out their roles in the government. Majority of the participants significantly contribute to the delivery of public information services.

The study shows that the participants occupy leadership positions and are tasked with ensuring the implementation of programs by their respective agencies. They are team leaders supervising staff that are involved in the program implementation.

The participants are also engaged in policy development and project proposal approval.

The study shows that as former members of the “fourth estate,” the participants remain committed to carry over and keep the press’ watchdog tradition – always being on a lookout to ensure the transparent and accountable delivery of public service. It is seen that former media practitioners in the government service are becoming agenda setters and watchdogs in their respective agencies with a battle cry and serious advocacy of pushing for transparency and accountability in public service delivery.

5. Suggestions to Strengthen Partnership to Curb Corruption, and Promote Transparency and Accountability in the Bureaucracy

The open access or the delivery of trusted and fact-based information emerges as the participants’ leading suggestion to help strengthen their engagement with the government in terms of curbing corruption, and promoting transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy. Providing full information access to public, and the strict observance of government processes and procedures are essential to the promotion of transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy.

The sense of values in terms of untainted integrity, and credible reputation; and commitment to public trust; and the implementation of transparency mechanisms/initiatives are also proposed.

Moreover, the creation of open data platforms; the establishment of public reporting systems that allow citizens to access information about the government operations, and spending; and hiring of former media practitioners as consultants, and media training/immersion are suggested.

6. Policies to be Recommended for Promotion of Transparent and Accountable Public Service Delivery.

The study shows that first two policies proposed by the participants are: Accelerating Communications’ Level in Government Agencies; and the Strengthening of the FOI.

Most participants believe that level of communications in government agencies must be accelerated through the use of digital technology, and that the institutionalization of regular conduct of press conferences and media briefings in all government agencies may be considered. The participants agreed that the FOI must be strengthened to fully enhance public information delivery, and promote the culture of transparency and accountability in the country.

Next to these proposals is the hiring of media professionals in government, given that these practitioners can significantly contribute to government's transparency and accountability bid due to their skill set, exposure and trainings.

Amid the fast-paced digital technology, the continued skills upgrading for government communicators for them to effectively communicate policies, and programs in the public sector is also pushed.

The creation of fora where government communicators can share best practices in communicating government policies and programs is also stressed to help ensure synchronized communications plans of all agencies and institutions in the public sector.

The participants also cited that the promotion of transparency and accountability in the government does not only rest on the shoulders of the former media practitioners and media sector, but to all Filipinos.

Other recommendations include the media involvement in the government process, such as policymaking, evaluation and monitoring of best practices, and social media regulation. The creation of an independent body, composed of former media practitioners, that will keenly monitor government agencies' pro-transparency and accountability efforts is recommended. The government's provision of grants for investigative journalism projects is also encouraged.

Conclusions

The following key points are presented based on the findings of this study:

1. The participants of the study are mostly female and print journalists, and are Millennials and Generation X with an extensive media experience of 10 to 20 years, and are now predominantly working in agencies under Executive branch of government holding permanent and supervisory positions.

2. The participants left their media profession mainly due to economic reasons, and that higher compensation, security of tenure, and proper provision of benefits in the government attracted them to join the government service.

The lack of benefits in the media sector (such as overtime and hazard pay and night differential, retirement package, insurance, enough transportation allowance, and healthcare protection scholarships, and trainings), is identified as major reason behind their migration to government. This is followed by low compensation and absence of clear tenure.

3. The study articulates that those former media practitioners who are currently working in government are very much involved in the delivery of public information services as public communicators for the policies and programs being implemented by agencies under the Executive and Legislative branches of government.

It is also concluded that the mandate of the agency-employers influenced the participants' roles in government service.

4. The participants' negative perception about the government changed or their initial view of government service was reinforced when they entered and immersed themselves in the government service, particularly in the delivery of public services.

The participants make sure they exemplify professionalism, competence, ethics, dedication and commitment to public trust when fulfilling their roles.

The study highlights that providing accurate, credible and precise information in an efficient, timely and professional manner is a form of public service delivery that must be prioritized.

Moreover, it is acknowledged that the continued quest for transparency and accountability in the delivery of public service remains, and that more work still needs to be done to enhance transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy.

5. It is concluded that the expertise and skills set of former journalists can be of significant help to ensure efficient, transparent, prompt, and accountable delivery of public service delivery, particularly in the area of public information services. The participants are government assets that should be fully tapped to reinforce the principles of transparency and accountability, and bring the government closer to people through the delivery of credible, prompt and accurate public information services.

Furthermore, it is affirmed that the participants significantly contribute to the delivery of public information services as government communicators, and as lead persons in the implementation of some government programs.

The participants' leadership positions and their crucial duties and roles in ensuring the implementation of programs by their respective agencies, and their involvement in policy development and project proposal approval showed they have major influence on the delivery of government services, while keeping the fourth estate's watchdog tradition to ensure the transparent and accountable delivery of public service.

6. The study highlights that providing full information access to public, and the strict observance of government processes and procedures are essential to the promotion of transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy.

The former practitioners' sense of values in terms of untainted integrity, and credible reputation; and commitment to public trust should be instilled and that transparency mechanisms/initiatives such as the creation of open data platforms, the establishment of public reporting systems that allow citizens to access information about the government operations, and spending should be pursued.

7. The study underscores the pressing need to accelerate the level of communications in government agencies through the use of digital technology; and to institutionalize the regular conduct of press conferences and media briefings in all

government agencies. The strengthening of FOI to fully enhance public information delivery and promote the culture of transparency and accountability in the country is highlighted.

The hiring of media professionals in government, the continued skills upgrading for government communicators for them to effectively communicate policies, and programs, and creation of fora where government communicators can share best practices in communicating government policies and programs are pressed on.

It is also stressed that the promotion of transparency and accountability in the government does not only rest on the shoulders of the former media practitioners and media sector, but to all Filipinos.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and in light of conclusions drawn, the following significant points are recommended:

1. Consider mapping out the total number of Filipino journalists and former media practitioners in the country. A data repository is warranted as there is no available, and official data yet on the total number of journalists from the private sector who entered the government service, the data on the total number of Filipino journalists who lost their jobs or resigned during the pandemic, and who entered the government service.

2. Consider pushing for reforms enhancing media workers' welfare to foster a healthy media environment. This includes the Congress' revival of the proposed Media Workers' Welfare Act that was passed on third and final reading by the House of Representatives in 2022.

3. Reinforce former media practitioners' contributions to public service delivery by not stereotyping them as communication or media relations officers, but giving them opportunities to assume other key roles related to substantive policy work or policy-making and to be involved in the government processes such as evaluation, review, and approval of government's plans, programs, and projects.

4. Intensify public information campaign on what the government is doing for the people; all agencies are encouraged to aggressively pursue an information campaign to change the bad perception against the government.

Seriously instill professionalism, competence, ethics, dedication and commitment to public trust among public sector workers. Republic Act No. 6713 or the "Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees" should serve as the bible of all public servants to promote a high standard of ethics in public service. The Code declares that public officials and employees "shall discharge their duties with utmost responsibility, integrity, competence, and loyalty; act with patriotism and justice; lead modest lives; and uphold public interest over personal interest." Public servants must be fully committed to uphold the time-honoured principle of public office being a public trust.

The Public Information Offices (PIOs) of all government agencies and institutions are likewise prodded to exhaust all means to provide accurate, credible and precise information in an efficient, timely and professional manner.

Furthermore, since continued quest for transparency and accountability in the delivery of public service remains, the creation an independent body, composed of former media practitioners, that will keenly monitor government agencies' pro-transparency and accountability efforts may be considered.

5. Consider tapping former journalists who are in the government service or current veteran journalists to conduct trainings and seminars among PIO staff and journalists covering government agencies and institutions as their beat assignments, and consider providing them honorarium or incentives.

Encourage media consultations or consider involving media or former media practitioners working in the government in the government process, such as in policymaking, and in the evaluation and approval of government projects.

Noting that former media practitioners have major influence on the delivery of government services, reinforcing their contributions by opening up opportunities for leadership roles, such as managerial or supervisory posts may be considered.

6. Prod all PIOs of all government agencies to ensure that their official websites fully conform to full transparency, and pattern it after the websites of the Commission on Audit (COA), Sandiganbayan, and the Supreme Court (SC). Since providing full information access to public is important, and that the strict observance of government processes and procedures are essential to the promotion of transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy, such recommendation is strongly recommended.

The sense of values in terms of untainted integrity, and credible reputation; and commitment to public trust should be instilled to all government communicators.

Transparency mechanisms/initiatives such as the institutionalizing the creation of open data platforms among state agencies and institutions; and the establishment of public reporting systems that allow citizens to access information about the government operations, and spending are encouraged.

7. Accelerate communications' level in government agencies. In pursuing this recommendation, the use of digital technology and infrastructure should be seriously considered.

Consider institutionalizing the regular conduct of press conferences and media briefings in all government agencies. This provides avenue for the government agencies to update the public about their plans, programs, and projects and other initiatives, as well answer the pressing concerns and issues hounding their agencies. This will help improve

media and public access to crucial public data and information towards well-informed citizenry.

Drum up campaign support for the strengthening of Freedom of Information (FOI) to convince President Marcos Jr. to sign a written order or an executive order directing government institutions to deepen their commitment to FOI principles. This will help ensure an increased approval of FOI requests made by the public in a bid to fully enhance public information delivery and promote the culture of transparency and accountability in the country

Consider the regularization of experienced media practitioners who are holding coterminous positions, and are hired under the Job Order and Contract of Service status with their extensive media experience as a major factor of providing plantilla positions for them.

Prioritize skills upgrading and conduct trainings among the PIO officers and staff members, and journalists who cover the departments/agencies. There should be continued skills upgrading for public sector communicators for them to effectively communicate government policies, and programs and projects. Also, those reporters who are assigned to cover agencies are encouraged to undergo trainings and seminar to familiarize themselves with the agencies they cover and effectively report on their mandates, programs and projects.

Since this study stressed that the promotion of transparency and accountability in the government does not only rest on the shoulders of the former media practitioners and media sector, but to all Filipinos, all stakeholders, both the public and private sectors are encouraged to work hand-in-hand to enhance transparency and accountability in the bureaucracy.

Also consider the proposed Program on Strengthening the PIOs in Government Agencies created by the researcher based on the findings and insights and conclusions of this study. Amid the changing media landscape and the battle cry to promote transparency and accountability in the government through the provision of public information services, the implementation of the proposed program seeks to enhance the capacity of units or offices serving as information and communications arms of the public sector in delivering the much-needed data and information to the public, and in communicating government policies, programs, and projects and other initiatives. The program also intends to address the gaps and kinks in the delivery of public information services in the public sector.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured the integrity of research undertaking by strictly following ethical and professional standards set by the Graduate School. Protecting the privacy and dignity of participants was a priority, while ensuring the conduct of the research was

within the framework of ethical considerations: confidentiality, consent, and respect for the participants were adhered to.

The researcher formally sought a written or verbal permission from the participants before conducting the Zoom-aided interviews. Three (3) respondents managed to sign the Consent Certificate, while the rest opted to signify their voluntary participation by responding affirmatively to the e-mailed letter request, and by saying “Yes” before the start of the Zoom-recorded interview.

The purpose of the study has been explained to the respondents in various communication channels. Before conducting the interview, the researcher made sure that the respondents positively responded and voluntarily gave their consent to be part of the study. The researcher likewise assured the participants that confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity were strictly observed, and that Zoom recordings both audio and video, and all data and information collected were solely used for the research analysis, and scholarly pursuits.

The participants were given the leeway, time, and avenue to express their views and opinions freely. The researcher upheld the highest ethical standards without compromising the validity and reliability of the study’s findings.

The participants’ statements were treated with utmost confidentiality and anonymity through the use of coded aliases during the data analysis.

The participants’ names, media organizations, government agency-employers and current specific positions were not disclosed and were kept confidential. The 15 respondents were given aliases (P1 to P15).

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